

University of
Strathclyde
Glasgow

DEPARTMENT OF MATHEMATICS AND STATISTICS

**Modelling regional variation in dementia mortality across the
Netherlands: a spatial analysis of environmental and socio-
economic factors**

by

Manuela Cocco

MSc Applied Statistics

2024/25

Statement of work in project

The work contained in this project is that of the authors and where material from other sources has been incorporated full acknowledgement has been given.

Signed

Print Name Manuela Cocco

Date 23 June 2025

Supervised by Dr. Silvia Malagoli

Contents

1	Introduction	2
2	Methods	5
2.1	Data	5
	Mortality Data	5
	Environmental Data	6
	Meteorological Data	7
	Deprivation Data	7
2.2	Direct standardisation of mortality	8
2.3	Principal Component Analysis (PCA)	9
2.4	Spatial Analysis	9
2.5	Statistical analysis	11
	Model 1: Multilevel model with region-varying slopes	12
	Model 2: Spatial hierarchical model with BYM2 structure	13
	Model Comparison: Leave-One-Out Cross-Validation (LOO-CV)	14
	Moran's I statistics on residuals	14
	Model's Diagnostics	15
	Prior predictive checks	15
	Posterior predictive checks	15
	Standardisation	16
2.6	Sensitivity analysis for COVID-19	16
2.7	Data and code availability	16
3	Results	17
3.1	Data visualisation and descriptive statistics	17

3.2 PCA analysis for model input 22

3.3 Results of the models 23

3.4 Sensitivity analysis for COVID-19 27

4 Discussion 29

5 Conclusions 35

References 37

Appendix A 45

Abstract

Background:

Dementia mortality exhibits considerable regional variation in the Netherlands, yet the roles of environmental, socio-economic, and meteorological factors in shaping this variation remain insufficiently understood. This study systematically investigates these influences at the population level using Bayesian spatial modelling.

Methods:

An ecological, region-level analysis was conducted across all 40 COROP regions in the Netherlands for 2014-2022. Age- and sex-standardised dementia mortality was calculated using the Comparative Mortality Figure (CMF). Regional predictors included composite air pollutant and industrial emissions indices derived via principal component analysis (PCA), socio-economic status (SES), population density, and meteorological variables. Two Bayesian hierarchical models, a multilevel model with region-varying slopes and a spatial model with a modified Besag-York-Mollié (BYM2) structure, were fitted to quantify associations, control for spatial autocorrelation, and identify the best-fitting approach using Leave-One-Out Cross-Validation (LOO-CV).

Results:

Marked regional disparities in dementia mortality persisted after standardisation. The strongest and most consistent predictor of higher dementia mortality was a composite pollutant index (PC4) dominated by ozone, cadmium, and ammonia; each standard deviation increase in PC4 was associated with a 2.3% increase in CMF (95% CI: 0.1%, 4.4%), indicating higher pollutant levels correspond to increased risk. Population density independently amplified risk, with a 5.3% increase in CMF per standard deviation (636 people/km²). Meteorological conditions, particularly higher sunshine and rainfall, were modestly protective, while higher sea-level pressure increased risk. The optimal model (region-varying slopes) explained most spatial structure but overestimated mortality, highlighting unexplained residual regional differences. Sensitivity analyses underscored the distorting effects of COVID-19 on recent mortality patterns.

Conclusions:

Dementia mortality in the Netherlands is shaped by a complex interplay of pollutant mixtures, urban density, and meteorological conditions. Future work should integrate individual-level data to clarify causal pathways and inform targeted dementia prevention strategies.

1 Introduction

Dementia is an overall term that define a range of progressive neurological disorders that impact brain function. These disorders affect memory, language, motor skills, object recognition, and reasoning, ultimately interfering with daily activities (1). Among the various types, Alzheimer disease (AD) is the most prevalent, accounting for 60–80% of cases (2). It is characterised by the accumulation of proteins plaques and tangles in the brain that accompany neuronal degeneration (3). Vascular dementia (VaD), the second most common type, accounts for up to 20% of cases and results from restricted cerebral blood flow due to conditions such as stroke, hypertension or diabetes (4).

Global demographic ageing is driving a sharp increase in dementia cases. The number of individuals with Alzheimer's disease and other dementia rose from 19.79 million in 1990 to 51.62 million in 2019, a 160.84% increase (5). Projections estimate this number will reach 152.8 million by 2050, despite a stable age-specific prevalence (6). While global incidence rates do not differ by sex, women bear a higher prevalence (6,7), partly due to differences in life expectancy and educational attainment (8).

In Europe, the age-standardised prevalence of dementia is approximately 6.4%, increasing from 0.8% among individuals aged 65–69 to nearly 29% in those over 90 (7). In the Netherlands, an estimated 277,000 people were living with dementia in 2019. This number is projected to rise by 78%, reaching approximately 493,000 by 2050 (6). In 2022, mental and neurological disorders were the third leading cause of death in the country, following cancer (28%) and cardiovascular disease (23%). According to Statistics Netherlands (CBS), approximately 22,200 deaths, representing roughly 13 percent of all deaths, were attributed to this category (9). When examining specific underlying causes, dementia was the primary contributor of death among women (12.2%) and the second among men (6.6%), following lung cancer (10). Since 2012, dementia has consistently been the most common cause of death in the Netherlands, excluding COVID-19 (11). In 2022, the Netherlands recorded also the second highest rate of dementia-related deaths among European countries, according to Eurostat data (Figure 1).

Beyond ageing, environmental exposures to air pollutants have been implicated in neurodegeneration (12,13). A 2025 burden-of-proof meta-analysis reported a 14 % increase in dementia risk across common European PM_{2.5} concentration levels (14). In a national Dutch cohort of over 10 million individuals, long-term ambient air pollution was associated with increased neurodegenerative mortality (15). However, findings remain inconsistent; for instance, the population-based Rotterdam Study reported no clear association between

common pollutants and risk of dementia (16). Many studies still evaluate air pollutants individually and rarely incorporate industrial compounds as potential contributors.

Socio-economic conditions represent another vulnerability. Dutch cohort studies show that individuals in the lowest income tertile experience up to 41% higher mortality after a dementia diagnosis compared with their wealthier peers (17). These disparities likely reflect cumulative disadvantages in education, occupation, and healthcare access. However, their role in explaining spatial variation in dementia mortality remains underexplored.

Demographic pressure itself may also modify dementia risk. A neighbourhood-level study in the UK Biobank reported a 10% increase in incident dementia per 1,000 units/km² increase in residential density, even after adjusting for individual-level socio-economic factors (18).

Evidence from the Netherlands is limited to small-area studies or all-cause mortality and does not assess interactions between population density and complex pollution mixtures, a critical gap in a densely populated country (19) where industrial plants, traffic corridors and residential areas often coexist.

To our knowledge, no study has yet integrated air pollution, industrial emissions, meteorological factors, socio-economic status, and population density within a single spatial framework in the Netherlands. This study addresses this gap using data from all 40 *COördinatiecommissie Regionaal OnderzoeksProgramma* (COROP) regions, administrative units that offer a practical scale for policy intervention (Figure 2).

To achieve this, annual mortality data for 2014–2022 were aggregated to the 40 COROP regions and converted into age- and sex-standardised dementia-mortality ratios. Region-level predictors were ambient-pollution and industrial-emission mixture, population density and deprivation indexes. Meteorological variables were used as confounding. Two Bayesian spatial models, a multilevel model with region-varying pollutant slopes and a spatial hierarchical model with a modified Besag-York-Mollie (BYM2) structure (18,19), estimated exposure-mortality association.

This ecological study aims to:

1. Describe age- and sex-standardised dementia mortality across the 40 COROP regions of the Netherlands (2014–2022).
2. Estimate the associations of regional-level predictors with dementia-mortality risk, controlling for meteorological confounding.
3. Compare explanatory performance and spatial fit of the two Bayesian models.

Figure 1. Eurostat: standardised death rates from dementia in Europe, 2022. Age-standardised death rates per 100,000 inhabitants aged 65 and over for dementia (ICD-10 codes F01–F03) by country. The Netherlands recorded the second highest rate among 34 European countries, following Malta.

Source: Eurostat. Reproduced from:

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/hlth_cd_asdr2_custom_17157408/default/map?lang=en accessed [17 June 2025].

Figure 2. Map of the Netherlands by COROP region.

Administrative map showing the 40 COROP regions, used for regional statistical analysis in the Netherlands. Each region is labelled with its COROP code. See Supplementary Table 1 in Appendix A for full region names and codes.

2 Methods

This study has been conducted as a spatial ecological study, where both exposures and outcomes are observed at the population level, where the unit of analysis are geographical regions. A spatial ecological approach examines geographical variations in health outcomes and their association with environmental factors (20). Specifically, regional aggregates of environmental pollution, socio-economic factors, and meteorological variables were linked to area-level mortality from dementia across Dutch regions. In this design, all variables and outcomes are summarised for each spatial unit, defined by COROP regions which correspond to NUTS-3 regions at the European level, and associations are interpreted at this aggregated population level. NUTS refers to the Nomenclature of Units for Territorial Statistics (21), which is a hierarchical system developed by the European Union to standardise territorial divisions for statistical and administrative purposes across its member states.

Ecological studies are valuable because they allow researchers to investigate associations between exposures and outcomes at the population level, often spanning large geographic areas or extended time periods. They also are typically cost-effective and efficient, as they make use of routinely collected data. However, a key limitation of ecological studies is that associations identified at the group or regional level cannot be directly attributed to individuals within those groups, which is called ecological fallacy (22). Furthermore, most ecological data have some degree of spatial structure (23), as neighbouring regions may share similar characteristics, which is known as the first law of geography: “Everything is related to everything else, but near things are more related than distant things” (24). This spatial correlation has to be addressed in the analysis.

The study covers the period from 2014 to 2022, with all data aggregated at annual intervals.

All analyses were performed using R Statistical Software version 4.4.3 (25).

2.1 Data

Mortality Data

Mortality data were sourced from Statistics Netherlands (CBS) (26) using the R package `cbsodataR` (27), they were directly standardised and expressed as Comparative Mortality Figure (CMF), a ratio calculated to remove the effects of different age and sex distributions across populations, which allows for comparisons across regions and over time. This adjustment ensures that variations in mortality reflect actual differences in health outcomes

rather than differences in population age and sex structure. A detailed explanation is provided in Section 2.2.

The population studied comprises women and men that are 65 and older.

Causes of death were retrieved from CBS where they were classified by the International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health problems, 10th revision (ICD-10) (28). The outcome was based on aggregated CBS mortality data using ICD-10 codes F01–F09 and F20–F99, i.e. mental and behavioural disorders excluding psychoactive substance use, consistent with the structure of the publicly released datasets. Although microdata would allow for more detailed cause-of-death classifications, this study intentionally relied on publicly available open data, as restricted access and ethical approval requirements for microdata were beyond the scope of this research.

Environmental Data

Air pollutant concentrations were extracted from the *European air quality data (interpolated data) - Series (eea_aq-interpolated_s)* maps provided by the European Environmental Agency (EEA) (29), which uses a Regression-Interpolation-Merging Mapping (RIMM) methodology at a 1 km grid resolution. This approach integrates monitoring data, chemical transport model outputs, and satellite observations, and uses a linear regression model followed by ordinary kriging of its residuals, which captures spatial structures (30).

The data is available on an annual basis and includes mean estimates for pollutants relevant to human health. Particulate matter with a diameter less than 10 µm (PM10) is represented as the annual average of the 90.4th percentile of daily means (in µg/m³). Annual averages in µg/m³ are also provided for particulate matter with a diameter less than 2.5 µm (PM2.5), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), and nitrogen oxides (NO_x). Ozone (O₃) is assessed using the sum of means over 35 ppb (SOMO35), expressed in µg/m³-days, which is calculated as the sum, across all days in a year, of the daily maximum 8-hour mean concentrations exceeding 35 ppb (equivalent to 70 µg/m³).

The 90.4th percentile of daily PM10 concentrations indicates how pollution levels compare to the EU Air Quality Directive (31) daily limit of 50 µg/m³, where exceedances of this limit are permitted on up to 35 days per year (calculated as $(365 - 35)/365 = 0.904$).

These gridded pollutant estimates were subsequently averaged at the COROP regional level.

Industrial emissions were extracted from the *EEA Industrial Reporting geospatial database of the European Pollutant Release and Transfer Register (E-PRTR) of 10 March 2025* (version 14) and reported in kg/year (32). The E-PRTR includes data on 91 pollutants, with annual reports submitted by approximately 30,000 industrial facilities across the EU. Air pollutants considered were mercury and compounds (Hg), lead and compounds (Pb), cadmium and compounds (Cd), arsenic and compounds (As), polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), benzene, carbon monoxide (CO), non-methane volatile organic compounds (NMVOC), sulphur oxides (SO_x), methane (CH₄) and ammonia (NH₃).

These pollutants were chosen because previous studies have linked them, and the secondary pollutants they help create, to dementia and other mental disorders (33–38).

Pollutant releases were summed across all facilities within each COROP region.

Because many of the pollutants and industrial emissions were strongly correlated, they were combined into several composite indicators using Principal Component Analysis.

R packages *terra* (39) and *sf* (40,41) were used.

Meteorological Data

Meteorological data, such as air temperature (°C), global horizontal irradiance (W/m²), mean sea level pressure (hPa), total precipitation (m), and wind speed at 10 m height (m/s), were sourced from the *Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) operational energy dataset* (42). These data capture annual averages and accumulated measures at the provincial level NUTS-2. This level of detail was considered appropriate for this analysis, as meteorological variables do not show variability at small scales as the COROP/NUTS-3.

Deprivation Data

Socio-Economic Status (SES-WOA) (43) and population density data from 2014 to 2022 were obtained from CBS (44,45).

SES-WOA stands for “*Socio-Economische Status - Woonsituatie, Opleidingsniveau en Arbeidsmarktpositie*”. It is a composite indicator developed to measure the socio-economic status of populations in the Netherlands, at various geographical levels (such as municipality, district, or neighbourhood). The SES-WOA indicator provides a single score that reflects how a municipality, district, or neighbourhood compares to others in the Netherlands in terms of socio-economic status. The indicator is based on three main domains: “*woonsituatie*” (housing situation), “*opleidingsniveau*” (level of education) and “*arbeidsmarktpositie*” (labour market

position). The average SES-WOA score for the Netherlands is set at 0 for the base year 2019. Scores above 0 indicate that the area is more prosperous, has a higher proportion of highly educated residents, and/or has a higher share of people in stable employment than the national average. Scores below 0 indicate relatively lower socio-economic status. The calculation method is standardised, so scores for other years are also comparable (46).

Population density was calculated as the average number of inhabitants per square kilometre for each COROP region and used as a proxy for rural-urban classification. Annual population counts and land area data for the period 2014–2022 were obtained from Statistics Netherlands (47).

For this study, mean SES-WOA scores and population density were aggregated to the COROP level for each year.

2.2 Direct standardisation of mortality

Comparisons of regional mortality due to dementia were made using the Comparative Mortality Figure, following the method of direct standardisation. The term “direct standardisation” is used because the actual age- and sex-specific mortality rates for each study population are directly applied to the standard population structure, producing an expected number of deaths for each region, as if it had the same demographic composition as the standard. This approach allows for fair and unbiased comparisons between regions, as each region is referenced to the same population structure (48,49). In this context, the standard population was defined as the mean Dutch population by age and sex, averaged over the period 2014–2022.

The CMF represents the expected deaths divided by observed deaths in standard population and was calculated according to (48) for each region:

$$CMF = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^s r_j N_j}{\sum_{j=1}^s R_j N_j} \quad (1)$$

Where $r_j = d_j/n_j$ represents the age- and sex-specific mortality rate for group j in the study population, and d_j and n_j are respectively the number of deaths and of persons in the group j in the study population; $R_j = D_j/N_j$ represents the age- and sex-specific mortality rate for the group j in the standard population, and D_j and N_j are respectively the number of deaths and of persons in the group j in the standard population; s is the numbers of strata.

A CMF greater than 1 indicates higher mortality in the region compared to the standard, while a value less than 1 indicates lower mortality.

Epidemiological studies commonly use the Standardised Mortality Ratio (SMR), a measure based on indirect standardisation. The SMR is calculated by dividing the observed number of deaths in the study population by the number of deaths expected, based on age- and sex-specific rates from a standard population. This method is considered indirect because it applies the mortality rates from the standard population to the structure of the study population. Although SMR is commonly used, it is not suitable for comparing mortality across multiple regions. The SMR uses the age and sex structure of each study population as weights, resulting in non-comparable denominators and potentially misleading comparisons (48,49). In contrast, direct standardisation references all regions to the same standard, which is recommended when the intention is to compare mortality across several populations or areas.

2.3 Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

In order to simplify data structure and address issues of multicollinearity among predictors, Principal Component Analysis was used in this study. This approach is widely used in environmental epidemiology to reduce dimensionality and derive composite indicators that summarise the major patterns of co-emitted pollutants.

PCA was applied to a set of sixteen annual air pollutant and emission variables, PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, NO₂, NO_x, O₃, mercury, lead, cadmium, arsenic, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), benzene, carbon monoxide (CO), non-methane volatile organic compounds (NMVOC), sulphur oxides (SO_x), methane (CH₄), and ammonia (NH₃), to summarise multi-pollutant exposure profiles at the regional level. Before performing PCA, all variables were standardised to ensure comparability and equal weighting across different measurement units. For further details, see Section 2.5.

The analysis was conducted using the package `stats` in R (50). The number of principal components retained was determined using the Kaiser criterion (eigenvalues greater than 1) and inspection of the scree plot.

2.4 Spatial Analysis

Spatial statistical methods were employed to quantify and assess spatial structure in the distribution of dementia mortality across Dutch COROP regions during the study period. In

epidemiological research, spatial analysis is essential for identifying geographic clustering, understanding spatial diffusion processes, and distinguishing between spatially structured and unstructured variation (51).

Moran's I was calculated for the entire study period to evaluate the null hypothesis of spatial randomness in the outcome. The statistic measures how similar neighbouring regions are: positive values denote spatial clustering, negative values signify spatial dispersion, and values close to zero imply no spatial autocorrelation (52).

The definition of "neighbourhood" is a critical choice in spatial analysis. For this project, a Queen contiguity criterion was used, where two regions are considered neighbours if they share any boundary point (including corners), ensuring a comprehensive representation of spatial relationships at the COROP level. To address disconnected regions such as Zeeuwsch-Vlaanderen, which are geographically separated from the rest of the Netherlands, a snap distance of 2,200 metres was applied during the construction of the spatial weights matrix. This approach allows neighbouring relationships to be established between regions within the specified distance, ensuring that all regions are adequately connected within the spatial network (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Spatial neighbours network for Dutch COROP regions.
Blue lines indicate neighbour relationships between regions.

All spatial data processing were performed in R, using the *sf* package for handling spatial vector data, the *spdep* package (53,54) for spatial weights and Moran's I statistics, and the *ggplot2* package (55) for visualisation. Spatial boundaries for Dutch regions were obtained from the official CBS GeoPackage dataset and 2022 version was utilised (45).

2.5 Statistical analysis

To investigate the association between environmental, socio-economic, demographic and meteorological factors and mortality for dementia, we fitted two Bayesian hierarchical regression models using the R *brms* package (56–58), which implements Bayesian inference via Stan probabilistic programming language (59).

Bayesian inference is a statistical framework in which model parameters are treated as random variables, meaning that uncertainty about their true values is described by probability distributions. This approach incorporates prior knowledge, formalised as a prior distribution, and updates it with observed data (the likelihood function). The result is a posterior distribution that integrates both prior beliefs and empirical evidence. It uses Bayes' theorem that can be expressed as follows:

$$p(\phi|y) = \frac{p(y|\phi)p(\phi)}{p(y)}, \quad (2. a)$$

Where $p(y|\phi)$ is the likelihood function, which specifies the distribution of the data y under the model defined by the parameter ϕ ; $p(\phi)$ is the prior probability distribution and reflects our prior belief; and $p(\phi|y)$ is the posterior probability distribution which represents the uncertainty about the parameter ϕ after having seen the data y . $p(y)$ is the marginal distribution of the data and is a constant because does not depend on ϕ .

Equation (2.a) can also be written as:

$$p(\phi|y) \sim p(y|\phi)p(\phi), \quad (2. b)$$

In this context, we denoted the generic parameter as ϕ , while reserving θ exclusively for relative risks to avoid ambiguity.

As mortality is a non-contagious and rare event, we assumed that region death counts $\{y_{its}, i = 1, \dots, R; t = 1, \dots, T; k = m, w\}$, where i are the non-overlapping study regions, t the years, and k the sex, are independent Poisson λ random variables with parameters λ_{itk} , assumed constant within areas:

$$y|e, \theta \sim Poiss(\lambda = e\theta), \quad (3)$$

where the expected number of cases e , based on the overall incidence rate and the age adjusted population at risk in region i , year t and sex k (it assumes constant risk), is assumed to be modified by the relative risk θ in region i , year t and sex k .

Subscripts i , t , and k are omitted for notational simplicity.

For the reasons expressed in Section 2.2, we decided to use the average CMF as the relative risk of mortality.

In both models, the likelihood of the observed outcome was modelled as a normal distribution, with its mean linked to the predictors via a log link function. This specification allowed model coefficients to be interpreted as percentage changes.

Model 1: Multilevel model with region-varying slopes

The first model is a multilevel model that allows for random variation in both the intercept and the effect of covariates across regions. This approach enables the association between covariates and CMF to vary across regions, while adjusting for all other covariates.

To assess whether the association between each covariate and CMF varied by region, we systematically tested for interaction effects. For each covariate, we fitted a separate linear model including an interaction term between the covariate and region. The model was of the form:

$$CMF = Covariate \times Region, \quad (4)$$

The significance and variance explained by each interaction term were evaluated using analysis of variance (ANOVA) (60).

The final multilevel model is written as:

$$\ln(CMF) = \beta_0 + \mathbf{b}_{0i} + \mathbf{x}^T \boldsymbol{\beta} + \mathbf{z}^T \mathbf{b}_i, \quad (5)$$

Where β_0 is the overall intercept, \mathbf{b}_{0i} is the vector of region-specific random intercepts, $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ represents the fixed-effects coefficients, \mathbf{b}_i is the region-specific random slope, \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{z} are vectors of covariates, measured for each observation (e.g., region, year, and sex group), and are associated with fixed and region-specific effects, respectively.

The regression coefficients were modelled with normal priors:

$$\beta_0, \sim Normal(0, \sigma_0^2), \quad (5.1)$$

$$\mathbf{b}_{0i} \sim Normal(0, \sigma_{0i}^2), \quad (5.2)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\beta} \sim Normal(0, \sigma_p^2), \quad (5.3)$$

$$\mathbf{b}_i \sim Normal(0, \sigma_b^2), \quad (5.4)$$

while standard deviations of the random effects σ_{0i} and σ_b used Student-t priors:

$$\sigma_{0i} \sim Student^+(v_{0i}, \mu_{0i}, \tau_{0i}), \quad (5.5)$$

$$\sigma_b \sim Student^+(v_b, \mu_b, \tau_b), \quad (5.6)$$

With v degrees of freedom, mean μ and scale τ .

Details for each prior are presented in Supplementary Table 2.

Model 2: Spatial hierarchical model with BYM2 structure

The second model incorporates at the region level both a correlated heterogeneity (CH) component, which represents unknown or unobserved covariates that if observed would have a spatial structure, and an uncorrelated heterogeneity (UH) component (61), which models unstructured random effects.

Such model is known as a modified Besag-York-Mollié (BYM2) convolution model and is formulated as follows (62):

$$\ln(CMF) = \beta_0 + \mathbf{c}^T \boldsymbol{\beta} + \sigma \sqrt{1 - \rho} v + \sqrt{\rho} u, \quad (6)$$

Here, β_0 and $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ have the same description as in equation 5; \mathbf{c} is the vector of covariates for each observation; v and u are the unstructured and standardised spatially structured random effects for each region i , respectively; σ is the overall standard deviation for the combined error terms, and ρ , between 0 and 1, expresses how much variability comes from the spatial structure and from the random effect.

The model coefficients were modelled with the following priors:

$$\beta_0 \sim Normal(0, \sigma_0^2), \quad (6.1)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\beta} \sim Normal(0, \sigma_c^2), \quad (6.2)$$

The spatial component u_i was expressed with an Intrinsic Conditional Auto-Regressive (ICAR) prior distribution (62,63):

$$u_i \sim Normal\left(\frac{\sum_{i \sim j} u_j}{d_i}, \frac{\tau_i^2}{d_i}\right), \quad (6.3)$$

Where $i \sim j$ is the set of regions neighbouring i , d_i the number of neighbours of region i , $\sum_{i \sim j} u_j$ is the sum of the spatial effects of the neighbours of i , τ_i^2 is the overall variance. The mean of u_i is the average of its neighbours' values and its variance is inversely proportional to the number of neighbours.

$$v_i \sim \text{Normal}(0, 1) \quad (6.4)$$

The hyperparameters ρ and σ were expressed as follows:

$$\rho \sim \text{Beta}(a, b), \quad (6.5)$$

$$\sigma \sim \text{Student}^+(\nu, \mu, \tau), \quad (6.6)$$

With ν degrees of freedom, mean μ and scale τ .

Details for each prior are shown in Supplementary Table 2.

Model Comparison: Leave-One-Out Cross-Validation (LOO-CV)

To compare the predictive performance of the two Bayesian hierarchical models, Leave-One-Out Cross-Validation was employed using the Pareto-smoothed importance sampling (PSIS-LOO) approach (64). LOO-CV is a robust and widely recommended method for estimating out-of-sample predictive accuracy in Bayesian models, as it assesses how well each model predicts data points that were not used during model fitting.

The LOO-CV estimates were computed using the `loo` function (65) from the `brms` package, which implements the efficient PSIS-LOO algorithm for complex hierarchical models. For each model, the Expected Log Predictive Density (ELPD) was calculated by systematically leaving out each observation in turn, refitting the model, and evaluating the likelihood of the held-out data given the model trained on the remaining data. Models were compared based on their ELPD values, with higher ELPD indicating better predictive performance. Differences in predictive accuracy between models were assessed using the associated standard errors.

This cross-validation procedure allowed for a data-driven comparison of alternative model specifications, accounting for model complexity and avoiding overfitting (66).

Moran's I statistics on residuals

To assess the presence of residual spatial autocorrelation after model fitting, Moran's I statistic was calculated on the model residuals, which indicate the difference between observed and predicted values. For each fitted model, residuals were extracted and tested using the `spdep` package in R.

The Moran's I statistic tests whether residuals are more spatially clustered than would be expected by chance. A non-significant Moran's I indicates that spatial autocorrelation has been adequately addressed in the model, while a significant value would suggest remaining spatial dependence.

Model's Diagnostics

Model convergence was assessed using the potential scale reduction factor (\hat{R}), ensuring values were close to 1, as well as by visually inspecting trace plots. Effective sample sizes were monitored to confirm adequate mixing of the chains. Divergent transitions were addressed by refining the model specification and prior distributions, and by adjusting the `adapt_delta` and `max_treedepth` parameters as necessary.

Prior predictive checks

Prior predictive checks were conducted to ensure that the specified prior distributions produced plausible values for the outcome variable before incorporating any observed data. This process aimed to confirm that the priors did not imply impossible or highly implausible values and that they appropriately regularised the model while remaining sufficiently weakly informative (66,67). Priors were considered weakly informative when (68,69):

$$posterior\ SD > 0.1\ prior\ SD \quad (7)$$

Prior predictive simulations were performed by fitting the model using the `brms` package, based solely on the prior distributions and the specified model structure, without conditioning on the observed outcome.

Posterior predictive checks

Posterior predictive checks were performed to assess the adequacy of the fitted Bayesian hierarchical model and evaluate its ability to reproduce the observed data (66,67). This recommended practice in Bayesian modelling provides a flexible and interpretable means to identify lack of fit and to validate the plausibility of the model's predictions against the observed data.

Posterior predictive draws were generated from the fitted model using the R `tidybayes` package (70). These draws were exponentiated to return predictions on the original scale of the outcome in line with the log-link used in the regression model.

For each region, the 2.5th and 97.5th percentiles of the predicted outcome were calculated to provide a 95% posterior predictive interval. The observed outcome for each region was then compared to the corresponding interval to assess model fit. Regions where the observed outcome fell outside the posterior predictive interval were identified as potential outliers or areas of model misspecification.

The use of both prior and posterior predictive checks aligns with best practices for Bayesian workflow and model validation (71).

Standardisation

All variables were standardised prior to modelling, meaning that they were transformed to have a mean of zero and a standard deviation of one. This procedure ensures that all covariates are on the same scale, which is important for PCA and contributes to improved numerical stability in Bayesian estimation (72). Standardisation also facilitates the interpretation of regression coefficients (as effects per standard deviation) (72) and improves the mixing and convergence of Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) chains (73). To have consistent interpretation of regression, PCA coefficients were further standardised.

2.6 Sensitivity analysis for COVID-19

The main analyses were conducted using data for the entire period (2014–2022), without explicit adjustment for COVID-19. This approach was chosen to maximise statistical power, retain the most recent data, and allow for the examination of long-term spatial patterns.

However, to address the potential impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on mortality patterns, two sensitivity analyses were conducted. First, the primary analyses were repeated with the dataset restricted to the pre-pandemic period (2014–2019), excluding all data from 2020 onwards. Second, a binary indicator variable was introduced in the full dataset (2014–2022) to denote the pandemic years (2020–2022), coded as 1 for those years and 0 otherwise. These approaches were used to assess the robustness of the main findings and to explore the extent to which the inclusion of pandemic-affected years influenced model estimates.

2.7 Data and code availability

Data and R code for the analysis are publicly available from GitHub (<https://github.com/ManuelaCocco/dementia-mortality-spatial-modelling-NL>).

3 Results

3.1 Data visualisation and descriptive statistics

As outlined in the Methods, dementia-related deaths were identified using the aggregated ICD-10 codes F01–F09 (Organic, including symptomatic, mental disorders) and codes F20 – F99 (other mental and behavioural disorders). Importantly, codes F01–F03, representing dementia, accounted for 94.6% of all deaths within the F01–F99 category (Supplementary Table 3 in Appendix A). Thus, the results predominantly reflect deaths coded as F01–F03 (dementia other than Alzheimer’s disease), with minimal contribution from other mental disorder categories.

Average CMF for dementia, visualised in Figure 4 and benchmarked against the national mean for 2014–2022, reveal clear regional disparities across Dutch COROP regions for both women and men. Among women, the lowest CMF values occurred in *Kop van Noord-Holland* (CR18), *Flevoland* (CR40) and *Alkmaar en omgeving* (CR19), indicating mortality rates that were 42%, 40% and 34% lower than the national reference, respectively. Conversely, *Agglomeratie Haarlem* (CR21), *Zeeuwsch-Vlaanderen* (CR31) and *Het Gooi en Vechtstreek* (CR24) recorded the highest female CMF, corresponding to excess risks of 34%, 25% and 21%.

For men, the geographical pattern largely mirrored that seen in women. The lowest male CMF were identified in *Flevoland* (CR40), *Alkmaar en omgeving* (CR19) and *Kop van Noord-Holland* (CR18), reflecting mortality deficits of 41%, 30% and 28% relative to the national average. The highest figures occurred in *Zeeuwsch-Vlaanderen* (CR31), *Agglomeratie Haarlem* (CR21) and *Het Gooi en Vechtstreek* (CR24), translating into excesses of 30%, 24% and 22%. Comprehensive regional estimates are presented in Supplementary Table 4 in Appendix A.

Although these results point to substantial regional heterogeneity, differences between the sexes seems to be comparatively small. The regions that exhibit the greatest and least risk are almost identical for women and men, suggesting that similar local factors shape dementia mortality in both groups. Within any given region, female and male CMF values rarely diverge by more than 0.1; for example, in *Agglomeratie Haarlem* the female CMF of 1.34 exceeds the male value of 1.24 by 0.1, a margin that is minor compared with the overall 34 % elevation above the national benchmark. In short, the broad span of regional CMF values (0.58 to 1.34) far outweighs the moderate sex gap observed within regions, indicating that place of residence

Figure 4. Average Comparative Mortality Figure for dementia in the 40 COROP regions of the Netherlands, shown separately for (a) females and (b) males. Colours indicate the regional CMF relative to the national average (CMF = 1.00), with purple/blue showing lower-than-average mortality and yellow/green representing higher-than-average mortality. For both sexes, lower CMF values are observed in north-western regions (e.g., Kop van Noord-Holland and Alkmaar), and the central region of Flevoland, while higher values are found in the west (Haarlem), the south-west (Zeeuwsch-Vlaanderen), and in the central region of Het Gooi. Exact regional CMF values are indicated on each map.

may be more powerful determinant of dementia mortality than sex once age differences have been standardised.

Temporal trends in CMF from 2014 to 2022 are illustrated in Figure 5, with values presented separately for women and men and expressed relative to the overall mean for the period. Here, a CMF of 1 corresponds to the national average across all years. For both women and men, CMF values increased from 2014, reaching a peak in 2018 (with women consistently showing

Figure 5 . Trends in average Comparative Mortality Figure for dementia in the Netherlands from 2014 to 2022. Average CMF is shown separately for women (yellow) and men (blue), with values above 1 indicating higher-than-average mortality.

(a) SES

(b) Population density

Figure 6. Regional variation in (a) Socio-Economic Status (SES) and (b) population density across the 40 COROP regions of the Netherlands.

Panel (a) shows SES values, with higher values (yellow/green) indicating more advantaged regions and lower values (blue/purple) indicating greater disadvantage. Panel (b) displays population density (inhabitants per km²), with yellow/green indicating the most densely populated areas, primarily in the urbanised west, and purple the sparsest regions.

slightly higher values than men), before declining to their lowest levels in 2021. By 2022, the CMF had rebounded somewhat for both sexes, though it remained below the 2018 peak. Notably, while the overall temporal patterns were similar for both groups, women exhibited higher CMF values than men up to 2018, whereas from 2019 onwards, men's CMF values became slightly higher.

Distinct spatial patterns emerge when examining SES and population density across Dutch regions, as visualised in Figure 6. The left panel shows regional variation in SES, with higher values in yellow concentrated in the central and western parts of the country, particularly around Utrecht and parts of North Brabant. Lower SES values (shown in blue and green) are observed in the northern, eastern, and southern regions. This highlights a clear spatial pattern, with central and western regions generally characterised by higher socio-economic conditions. The right panel displays that the highest population densities are distinctly localised in the Randstad area, notably in the provinces of North Holland, South Holland, and Utrecht, while the remaining regions show much lower densities. This stark contrast underlines the urban-rural divide, with urbanised western regions being substantially more densely populated than other parts of the country.

Examination of Figure 7 reveals the spatial distribution of major air pollutants throughout the Netherlands, highlighting distinct geographic patterns in exposure. Both PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} concentrations are highest in the southern and western regions. Lower concentrations are

Figure 7. Spatial distribution of major air pollutants across COROP regions in the Netherlands. Each map shows the mean annual concentration for a specific pollutant from 2014–2022, with (a) PM10 ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), (b) PM2.5 ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), (c) NO₂ ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), (d) NO_x ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), and (e) ozone (O₃, $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^2\cdot\text{days}$). Colours range from purple (lowest concentrations) to yellow (highest concentrations). The highest concentrations of PM10, PM2.5, NO₂, and NO_x are observed in the southern and western urbanised regions, while the lowest are found in the northern and eastern rural regions. Ozone levels (panel e) show an opposite pattern, with higher values in the south-east and lower values in the north-western and urbanised areas.

observed in the northern and north-eastern parts of the country, highlighting a clear spatial gradient from urbanised to more rural regions. The maps for NO₂ and NO_x show a similar spatial pattern, with the highest levels again concentrated in the west and south-west, including the major urban and industrial areas. Northern and rural regions generally have much lower concentrations of these pollutants. In contrast to the other pollutants, ozone concentrations are highest in the southern and south-eastern regions, while the lowest levels are seen in the north and west. Spatial distribution of key environmental factors, air temperature, global horizontal irradiance, sea level pressure, total precipitation, and wind speed, across COROP regions is illustrated in Figure 8. Higher average air temperatures are observed in the southern and south-western regions, with values decreasing towards the north. This gradient reflects the influence of latitude and proximity to the North Sea. Total annual precipitation is relatively homogeneous across the Netherlands. Solar irradiance demonstrates a clear west–east gradient, with the highest values observed in the western and south-western regions, and lower levels towards the eastern and north-eastern parts of the country. This pattern indicates

Figure 8. Regional distribution of key meteorological variables across the 40 COROP regions of the Netherlands.

Maps display mean annual values for (a) temperature (°C), (b) global horizontal irradiance (W/m²), (c) sea level pressure (hPa), (d) total precipitation (m), and (e) wind speed (m/s) for the period 2014–2022. Colours represent the range of each variable, with yellow indicating higher values and purple indicating lower values.

that western regions receive more sunshine on average. Average wind speeds are greatest in the north and along the coastal regions, while the lowest wind speeds are found in the southern and central inland areas. Mean sea level pressure exhibits minor spatial variation but is slightly higher in the southern parts of the country compared to the north.

Supplementary Table 5 in Appendix A displays the correlation matrix for the main environmental and pollutant variables. PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, NO₂, and NO_x are highly positively correlated, reflecting their shared sources (mainly traffic and urban emissions). Population density is strongly positively correlated with NO₂ and NO_x, indicating higher concentrations of these pollutants in more densely populated regions. SO_x shows a positive correlation with NMVOC and benzene, suggesting common industrial or combustion-related sources. CO is positively correlated with heavy metals (Hg, As, Pb) and PAHs, which are also typically associated with incomplete combustion and industrial activities. O₃ is negatively correlated with precipitation, indicating that wetter regions tend to experience lower ambient ozone concentrations.

These patterns highlight the clustering of air pollutants by source, and underline how both environmental and socio-demographic factors structure spatial variation in pollutant exposure across regions.

3.2 PCA analysis for model input

Four principal components were retained for analysis, collectively accounting for approximately 73% of the total variance in the pollutant and emission data (Figure 9). The composition and loadings of these principal components are detailed in Supplementary Table 6 in Appendix A.

Among them, PC1 is dominated by positive loadings for heavy metals and toxic compounds (Hg, Pb, As, CO, SO_x). It represents a general pollution factor, capturing regions where high concentrations of a broad mixture of combustion, and industrial pollutants co-occur. PC2 is characterised by strong positive loadings on PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, NO₂, and NO_x, and negative loadings on PAHs and CO. This component appears to represent a contrast between particulate and nitrogen-based pollutants (typically associated with traffic and industrial emissions) and compounds related to combustion processes. PC3 is defined by positive loadings on benzene, NMVOC, and SO_x, and negative loadings on PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀. This suggests that PC3 distinguishes between regions with higher concentrations of volatile organic compounds and sulphur oxides, both markers of industrial activities, and those with higher levels of particulate pollution. PC4 is characterised by strong positive loadings for ozone,

Figure 9. Scree plot showing the proportion of variance explained by each principal component. The cumulative variance explained by the first four components (PC1–PC4) is 73.4%.

cadmium compounds, and ammonia. PC4 appears to capture variation associated primarily with ozone levels and certain agricultural or industrial pollutants.

3.3 Results of the models

In this study, two Bayesian models were employed to explore the association between environmental, socio-economic, and meteorological variables with dementia mortality across Dutch regions. Although both models included the same set of predictors, they differ in their treatment of spatial structure and regional variability. Model 1 is a multilevel regression model that allows the effect of some predictors to vary by region. Specifically, PC1 was selected for region-specific slope, as it exhibited the strongest evidence of region-level heterogeneity in its association with CMF (see Supplementary Table 7). Model 2, by contrast, is a spatial hierarchical model based on the BYM2 framework. This approach accounts for random variation between regions and incorporates spatial dependence, so that information is shared across neighbouring areas.

For both models, continuous covariates were standardised prior to analysis and each estimated coefficient (whether fixed or random effect) was exponentiated for interpretation. The exponentiated values represent the multiplicative effect on the CMF (i.e., the percentage change) associated with a one standard deviation increase in the corresponding predictor, holding all other variables constant at their mean value.

In Model 1, across the fixed effects, several predictors showed strong associations with CMF (Table 1). Principal Component 4 was significantly associated with CMF (1.023, 95% CI: 1.001 to 1.044), corresponding to a 2.3% increase in CMF per unit increase in PC4. PC4 was positively loaded on ozone, cadmium, and ammonia, indicating that higher concentrations of these pollutants are associated with higher PC4 scores and higher mortality. The lower bound of the 95% confidence interval (1.001) lies very close to the value of 1.00. Although the association is statistically significant, the effect size is modest and should be interpreted with caution.

Random effects indicated significant regional heterogeneity in the effects of PC1 which showed a significant positive relationship with mortality in *Agglomeratie 's-Gravenhage* (CR26) (1.132, 95% CI: 1.031 to 1.239), indicating that one standard deviation increase in PC1 (2.16 units) was associated with a 13.2% increase in CMF, all the other covariates fixed at their mean value. PC1 was positively loaded on mercury, lead, arsenic, carbon monoxide, and sulphur oxides, indicating that higher concentrations of these pollutants are associated with higher PC1

scores and higher mortality. This implies that the region of The Hague experiences higher dementia mortality with higher levels of the mentioned pollutants exposure. Specifically, moving one standard deviation towards higher pollutant concentrations is expected to raise CMF by approximately 13%, making the composite pollution index the largest single positive driver of dementia mortality in our model. No significant associations were observed for PC2 and PC3.

Also, population density was positively associated with mortality. One standard deviation increase in population density (636 people per km²) was associated with a 5.4% increase in CMF (1.053, 95% CI: 1.006 to 1.101).

Several meteorological variables also showed significant associations with CMF. One standard deviation increase in global horizontal irradiance (5.8 W/m²) was associated with a 4.6% reduction in CMF (0.954, 95% CI: 0.930 to 0.980). Similarly, one standard deviation increase in total annual precipitation (0.0878 m or 8.78 cm) corresponded to a 5.1% decrease in CMF (0.949, 95% CI: 0.931 to 0.967). In contrast, one standard deviation increase in mean sea level pressure (1.24 hPa) was associated with a 2.4% increase in CMF (1.024, 95% CI: 1.011 to 1.038).

No significant associations were observed for air temperature, sex or SES.

Table 1. Regression results for Model 1 with fixed and region-specific varying effects. Estimates are presented on the exponentiated scale, with 95% credible intervals. Bold values indicate effects whose 95% credible intervals do not include 1, and are therefore considered statistically significant under the Bayesian framework.

Regression Results			
Fixed and Region-Specific Significant Effects			
Effect Type	Variable	Estimate	95% Credible Interval
Fixed Effect	Intercept	0.980	0.937, 1.024
Fixed Effect	PC2	0.993	0.951, 1.036
Fixed Effect	PC3	1.020	0.979, 1.063
Fixed Effect	PC4	1.023	1.001, 1.044
Fixed Effect	Sex: Male	0.997	0.978, 1.016
Fixed Effect	Air Temperature	0.994	0.976, 1.013
Fixed Effect	Global Horizontal Irradiance	0.954	0.930, 0.980
Fixed Effect	Mean SES	0.972	0.930, 1.013
Fixed Effect	Mean Sea Level Pressure	1.024	1.011, 1.038
Fixed Effect	Population Density	1.053	1.006, 1.101
Fixed Effect	Total Precipitation	0.949	0.931, 0.967
Fixed Effect	Wind Speed	0.975	0.947, 1.004
Varying Effect	PC1 (CR26)	1.132	1.031, 1.239

Table 2. Regression results for Model 2 with BYM2 structure. Estimates are presented on the exponentiated scale, with 95% credible intervals. Bold values indicate effects whose 95% credible intervals do not include 1, and are therefore considered statistically significant under the Bayesian framework.

Regression Results Model 2		
Estimates and 95% Credible Intervals		
Variable	Estimate	95% Credible Interval
Intercept	0.978	0.936, 1.022
PC1	0.994	0.966, 1.023
PC2	0.995	0.967, 1.024
PC3	1.013	0.990, 1.037
PC4	1.014	0.993, 1.035
Sex: Male	0.996	0.977, 1.016
Air Temperature	0.994	0.975, 1.014
Global Horizontal Irradiance	0.959	0.934, 0.985
Mean SES	0.963	0.918, 1.009
Mean Sea Level Pressure	1.023	1.009, 1.038
Population Density	1.053	0.997, 1.110
Total Precipitation	0.951	0.933, 0.969
Wind Speed	0.982	0.950, 1.015

In Model 2, several variables were found to be significantly associated with dementia mortality (Table 2). Specifically, global horizontal irradiance was associated with a 4.1% decrease in dementia mortality risk for each standard deviation increase (0.959, 95% CI: 0.934–0.985) and total precipitation was associated with a 4.9% decrease in risk per one standard deviation increase (0.951, 95% CI: 0.933–0.969). Conversely, mean sea level pressure was associated with a 2.3% increase in dementia mortality risk per one standard deviation increase (1.023, 95% CI: 1.009–1.038). No statistically significant associations were observed for the air pollution principal components (PC1–PC4), population density, socio-economic status, or wind speed, as their credible intervals included 1.

As shown in Table 3, both models resulted in negligible residual spatial autocorrelation, with Moran’s I statistics close to zero (Model 1: -0.01, $p = 0.043$; Model 2: -0.01, $p = 0.036$). This suggests that nearly all spatial structure present in the outcome was effectively accounted for by both models.

Table 3. Comparison of the two main models: Model 1 includes region-varying slopes, whereas Model 2 incorporates a spatial CAR structure.

Model Comparison: Predictive Performance & Spatial Autocorrelation				
Model	ELPD difference	SE (diff)	Moran's I	Moran's I p-value
Model 1	0.00	0.00	-0.01	0.043
Model 2	-12.20	3.99	-0.01	0.036

Figure 11. Prior predictive distribution compared to observed data. The dark blue line represents the observed density of CMF, while the light blue lines represent simulated outcomes drawn from the prior predictive distribution. The alignment between prior predictions and the observed distribution indicates that the priors are appropriately specified and not overly restrictive.

materially affect the results: the overestimation of observed CMF values persisted. This outcome indicates that prior specification alone does not account for the observed discrepancy (Supplementary Table 9).

The prior predictive checks (Figure 11) demonstrated that the chosen priors were appropriate for the scale of the outcome and the predictors, and effectively ruled out implausible or extreme parameter values (Supplementary Table 10).

The prior-posterior standard deviation comparison for all model parameters (Supplementary Table 11) further confirmed that the priors were weakly informative, indicating that they regularised the model without overwhelming the data.

3.4 Sensitivity analysis for COVID-19

The two models, highlighted in Table 4, produced substantially different results. When the analysis was restricted to pre-pandemic years (2014–2019), only PC2 appeared statistically significant among the pollutant factors (0.958, 95% CI: 0.923 to 0.995), with the effects of all other pollutants substantially attenuated. This suggests that, compared with the national average, regions characterised by higher levels of nitrogen oxides and particulates, but lower levels of PAHs and CO, experienced lower mortality, after adjusting for all the other modelled factors.

Table 4. Sensitivity analysis of model with region-specific effects for dementia mortality across Dutch COROP regions, showing (a) estimates from the pre-COVID-19 period (2014–2019) and (b) estimates when including COVID-19 as a covariate (2014–2022).

The table reports fixed and region-specific effects, with point estimates and 95% credible intervals. Statistically significant associations (credible intervals not crossing 1) are highlighted in bold.

(a) Regression Model Results pre COVID				(b) Regression Model Results with COVID			
Fixed and Region-Specific Significant Effects				Fixed and Region-Specific Significant Effects			
Effect Type	Variable	Estimate	95% Credible Interval	Effect Type	Variable	Estimate	95% Credible Interval
Fixed Effect	Intercept	0.980	0.937, 1.025	Fixed Effect	Intercept	1.017	0.969, 1.066
Fixed Effect	PC2	0.958	0.923, 0.995	Fixed Effect	PC2	0.962	0.919, 1.006
Fixed Effect	PC3	0.974	0.946, 1.004	Fixed Effect	PC3	1.030	0.988, 1.073
Fixed Effect	PC4	1.015	0.987, 1.043	Fixed Effect	PC4	1.014	0.993, 1.035
Fixed Effect	Sex: Male	0.993	0.972, 1.016	Fixed Effect	Sex: Male	0.997	0.979, 1.016
Fixed Effect	Air Temperature	1.006	0.972, 1.041	Fixed Effect	Air Temperature	1.007	0.987, 1.026
Fixed Effect	Global Horizontal Irradiance	0.976	0.942, 1.009	Fixed Effect	COVID	0.897	0.851, 0.945
Fixed Effect	Mean SES	1.002	0.960, 1.048	Fixed Effect	Global Horizontal Irradiance	0.983	0.954, 1.013
Fixed Effect	Mean Sea Level Pressure	1.030	1.007, 1.055	Fixed Effect	Mean SES	0.990	0.947, 1.033
Fixed Effect	Population Density	1.071	1.019, 1.123	Fixed Effect	Mean Sea Level Pressure	1.027	1.013, 1.040
Fixed Effect	Total Precipitation	0.969	0.939, 0.999	Fixed Effect	Population Density	1.046	0.998, 1.095
Fixed Effect	Wind Speed	0.949	0.914, 0.984	Fixed Effect	Total Precipitation	0.975	0.953, 0.998
				Fixed Effect	Wind Speed	0.967	0.938, 0.996
				Varying Effect	PC1 (CR26)	1.128	1.032, 1.234

In contrast, when the COVID-19 indicator variable was included, it accounted for the majority of the explained variation, making the effects of all other fixed predictors negligible. Interestingly, however, PC1 was a significant positive predictor of mortality in the region of The Hague (CR26), with a 13% increase in mortality per standard deviation increase in PC1 (1.128, 95% CI: 1.032 to 1.234). Higher PC1 scores reflect regions with above-average exposure to these pollutants.

4 Discussion

This study investigated environmental and socio-demographic factors associated with mortality due to dementia across Dutch regions, using the Comparative Mortality Figure as a standardised outcome. A notable aspect of it was the comparison between two Bayesian modelling approaches, each offering a different perspective on spatial variation in dementia mortality. Model 1, the multilevel model with region-varying slopes, allowed the effects of a key predictor to differ across regions. This flexibility made it possible to detect both national-level associations and important localised effects such as the strong association between PC1 (heavy metals and combustion-related pollutants) and dementia mortality in Agglomeratie 's-Gravenhage. In contrast, Model 2, the spatial hierarchical model using the BYM2 structure, explicitly accounted for spatial dependence by smoothing risk estimates across neighbouring regions. While this approach effectively captured broad spatial trends and reduced noise due to random variation, it was less sensitive to localised effects. As a result, Model 2 identified only meteorological variables (global horizontal irradiance, total precipitation, and mean sea level pressure) as significantly associated with dementia mortality, and did not detect significant associations for the air pollution indices or population density. These differences may be attributed to the degree of spatial smoothing imposed by Model 2; over-smoothing can attenuate associations that are present only in certain regions or are highly variable across space (74).

The temporal trend in dementia mortality observed in Figure 5 appears closely linked to both epidemiological factors, such as severe influenza seasons and the emergence of COVID-19, and to changes in death certification practices implemented in response to the pandemic. In 2017 and 2018, the Netherlands experienced two consecutive severe influenza epidemics (75), with marked excess mortality due to respiratory illnesses, predominantly affecting older adults with existing comorbidities (76). According to the World Health Organization, the underlying cause of death is “the disease or injury which initiated the train of morbid events leading directly to death” (77). In practice, however, there is variability in how cause of death is certified in individuals with advanced dementia who die from acute events such as influenza: dementia is sometimes recorded as the underlying cause, particularly when it is judged to have contributed to the patient's overall vulnerability, while in other cases the acute event is listed. This variability can have important consequences for mortality statistics. During severe influenza seasons, excess winter mortality among frail older adults with dementia may therefore lead to an artificial inflation of deaths attributed to dementia. The observed rise in dementia mortality during these years does not necessarily indicate an increase in the

underlying prevalence of dementia, but may instead result from acute seasonal infections acting as triggers for death among vulnerable populations (76).

By contrast, the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic in early 2020 brought about a fundamental shift in international guidance for death certification. WHO issued explicit instructions that COVID-19 should be listed as the underlying cause of death whenever the infection precipitated death, regardless of pre-existing chronic conditions (78). Consequently, from 2020 onwards, deaths of people with dementia who died for COVID-19 were reclassified under ICD-10 codes U07.1–U07.2 (COVID-19) rather than under F01–F03 (dementia).

Multiple-cause-of-death analyses carried out by CBS for 2020–2022 reveal that dementia continued to play a significant role as a contributing cause among deaths officially certified as due to COVID-19. CBS reported that among individuals who died from COVID-19, the presence of dementia as a contributing cause was associated with a substantially higher risk of death. Specifically, women with dementia had a 33% higher risk (OR 1.33, 95% CI: 1.29–1.37), and men had a 41% higher risk (OR 1.41, 95% CI: 1.36–1.46), compared to their counterparts without dementia (10). However, these cases were no longer counted under dementia as the underlying cause of death, leading to a marked decline in the CMF for dementia in 2020–2021.

This pattern has been observed in other countries as well. For example, analyses in Chile have shown a similar reallocation of deaths from dementia to COVID-19 during the pandemic period, with an associated decline in dementia mortality rates that does not reflect a true improvement in outcomes for people with dementia, but rather a shift in the attribution of the underlying cause of death (79).

Furthermore, the observed differences between females and males might largely be attributed to underlying demographic and epidemiological patterns. Women generally tend to have higher dementia-related mortality than men, primarily because they live longer and are thus more likely to reach ages at which dementia is prevalent (80,81). In contrast, the impact of COVID-19 was more pronounced among men, who experienced higher mortality rates during the pandemic period (82,83). In the Netherlands specifically, the odds ratio for male-to-female for COVID-19 mortality was 1.33 (95% CI: 1.26 to 1.41) (84). However, an US study found that among women with comorbidities such as dementia or heart failure, the risk of dying from COVID-19 was greater than for men (OR 4.6, 95% CI: 3.9 to 5.4 versus 3.6, 95% CI: 3.0 to 4.3) (85). As a result, the typical pattern of higher dementia mortality among women was temporarily altered during the COVID-19 years.

It is worth noting that, the chosen model did not identify a statistically significant effect of sex, likely due to these opposing and temporally variable influences. These findings highlight the importance of accounting for both changes in cause-of-death certification practices and the disruptive effect of the COVID-19 pandemic when interpreting mortality trends for chronic conditions such as dementia.

Among the fixed effects, PC4 emerged as a predictor of CMF, with higher PC4 values linked to higher mortality (CMF = 1.023). PC4 had high positive loadings for ozone (O₃), cadmium (Cd), and ammonia (NH₃), representing a mixed environmental pollution factor. It indicates that higher PC4 values correspond to higher pollutant concentrations. Therefore, the model suggests that elevated levels of these pollutants may be associated with higher overall mortality from dementia.

Recent studies indicate links between exposure to these pollutants and elevated dementia risk. For example, an Italian study involving approximately 350,000 participants aged over 65 years, followed for 12 years, found a positive association between ozone exposure and dementia-related hospital admissions with hazard ratio of 1.061 per 10 µg/m³ of ozone exposure (86). Similarly, a Taiwanese cohort study demonstrated that approximately 11 parts per billion (ppb) increase in ozone exposure over 10 years corresponded to a 211% increased risk of Alzheimer's disease (87). A case-control analysis reported that older adults in the highest tertile of ozone or PM10 exposure had significantly higher odds of Alzheimer's and vascular dementia, approximately double the risk for ozone and four times higher for PM10, compared to those in the lowest exposure tertile (88).

The relationship between ozone and dementia risk remains complex and inconsistent across studies. For example, recent research from London, the United States, and Canada found either no positive association or even an inverse relationship between ozone and dementia, likely reflecting both methodological differences and the complex correlations between air pollutants (89–91). Such discrepancies may be due to collinearity and interactions when multiple pollutants are included in models, which can obscure the effect of any single pollutant. By applying principal component analysis, our study captured the combined influence of pollutants rather than attempting to estimate the effect of each pollutant separately. This approach may help explaining why our model identified an association with PC4, representing a mixture of ozone, cadmium, and ammonia, while studies focusing on individual pollutants have yielded mixed results.

Two nationally representative US cohorts provide consistent evidence that environmental cadmium exposure increases the risk of dementia mortality. In the Third National Health and

Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES), participants with high blood cadmium concentrations had a 3.8-fold higher hazard of death from Alzheimer's disease (AD) compared to those with low levels (92). A subsequent analysis using urinary cadmium reported a 58% increase in AD mortality per interquartile-range rise in urinary Cd, after adjustment for multiple confounders (93).

Gaseous ammonia from agricultural sources rapidly forms fine particulate ammonium salts (NH_4^+), which are increasingly linked to cognitive decline. In a cohort of 12 million U.S. Medicare beneficiaries, long-term exposure to the NH_4^+ fraction of PM_{2.5} was independently associated with increased incident dementia risk (hazard ratio = 1.07 per interquartile range increase) even after controlling for multiple pollutants (94).

To our knowledge, there are no published studies from the Netherlands examining the association between environmental cadmium or ammonia and dementia.

Beyond statistical associations, there are plausible biological mechanisms through which the pollutants in PC4 (ozone, cadmium, and ammonia) could contribute to dementia mortality. Ozone is known to induce oxidative damage in neuronal cells, neuroinflammation, and mitochondrial dysfunction, processes that are implicated in neurodegenerative diseases such as dementia (95). Cadmium is a well-documented neurotoxicant that is associated with cognitive impairment (96,97). Ammonia, largely emitted from agricultural activities, primarily livestock and animal production (98), can contribute to secondary particulate matter and, in extreme cases, can interfere with key neurotransmitter systems. It can also trigger inflammatory responses in the brain, which contributes to neuronal damage. These combined effects may explain the memory deficits and cognitive decline characteristic of dementia (99,100).

Using region-specific slopes for PC1 revealed meaningful spatial heterogeneity. PC1, which primarily reflects a pollution mixture dominated by heavy metals and combustion-related pollutants (with high loadings on mercury, leads, arsenic, sulphur oxides, and carbon monoxide), showed a significant region-specific association in *Agglomeratie 's-Gravenhage* (CR26). In this region, higher PC1 values (i.e., higher pollution) were associated with increased CMF (1.132), reinforcing the finding that air pollution has a measurable and harmful impact on dementia mortality, especially in dense urban environments like The Hague. This fact aligns with existing literature describing adverse relationships between industrial emissions and mental health outcomes. For example, a study conducted in a former industrial area in Portugal measured seven trace elements (Al, Mn, Fe, Cu, Zn, Hg, and Pb) in participants' hair. Mercury

concentrations displayed a clear upward trend, increasing progressively from healthy individuals to those with dementia (101).

A significant positive association between population density and dementia mortality was also identified at the country level. Several pathways could underlie this relationship. Densely populated areas typically experience higher traffic-related air pollutants and noise, both of which have been implicated in cognitive decline (90,102). Moreover, urban density often coincides with reduced access to green space and greater income inequality, each independently associated with psychiatric morbidity (103,104). Although our model adjusted for socio-economic status, residual confounding by unmeasured aspects of deprivation and health-care accessibility cannot be ruled out.

Meteorological conditions also emerged as relevant environmental influences. Greater global horizontal irradiance was associated with lower CMF (0.954), suggesting a protective role of sunlight. Similarly, total precipitation showed a negative association (0.949), which may reflect the role of rainfall in clearing air pollutants or affecting behavioural patterns (e.g., reduced outdoor exposure). By contrast, higher sea level pressure was associated with increased CMF (1.024), high-pressure regimes typically generate stagnant air masses with poor pollutant dispersion, which can amplify mortality risks (105).

Despite its good fit to the average trends in CMF, the model consistently overestimated regional mortality. Posterior predictive intervals failed to capture any of the observed CMF values, even after adopting wider prior distributions. This persistent discrepancy may indicate the presence of important sources of variation, such as unmeasured healthcare, social, or environmental factors, that were not included in the model.

The inclusion of data from 2020 to 2022, including the COVID-19 pandemic, represented a notable challenge for interpreting the results of this study. Sensitivity analyses indicated that the pandemic years had a dominant influence on mortality patterns: when the data were restricted to pre-pandemic years, most associations were no longer statistically significant, while models including a COVID-19 indicator variable showed that this variable absorbed nearly all explanatory power. These findings are consistent with previous research, which has shown that the pandemic caused increases in all-cause and cause-specific mortality, with its impact depending on healthcare system resilience, population health, and policy interventions (106). The presence of the pandemic period in the dataset likely introduced additional variability and may have obscured long-term relationships between environmental, climatic, and socio-economic factors and dementia mortality. It is important to interpret the results with this limitation in mind. The observed associations for the period 2014-2022 might, in part,

reflect the unique context and disruptions of the pandemic, rather than solely the underlying factors under investigation.

Several key strengths distinguish this work. First, the study integrates high-resolution, multi-source data on air pollution, industrial emissions, and meteorological factors, and it uses principal component analysis to address multicollinearity among highly correlated pollutants. In this way, the study captures real-world exposure scenarios more accurately and may reveal associations that are not apparent when pollutants are considered individually.

Moreover, employing Bayesian spatial modelling across all 40 COROP regions allowed for the quantification of spatial structure and heterogeneity in mortality risk. To our knowledge, this is the first study to utilise Bayesian spatial methods to investigate the association between dementia mortality and environmental, socio-economic, and meteorological factors at this regional scale in the Netherlands.

Additionally, the ecological design facilitated the comparison of broad regional patterns and the identification of high- and low-risk areas, providing actionable insights for public health planning.

Despite these strengths, several limitations should be acknowledged. The ecological study design, while enabling regional comparisons, inherently precludes inference at the individual level, raising the risk of ecological fallacy, where associations observed for regions may not hold for individuals within those regions.

As well, the use of aggregated open-access mortality data restricted outcome classification to broad ICD-10 groupings, precluding specific analysis of Alzheimer's disease (G30) and potentially limiting comparability with studies based on microdata or narrower diagnostic criteria.

Furthermore, although a wide array of covariates was included, the model's consistent overestimation of observed mortality in posterior predictive checks suggests the presence of unmeasured confounders. Factors such as regional differences in healthcare access, comorbidity patterns, and certain social or behavioural determinants could not be incorporated due to the lack of region-level and individual data.

Lastly, while the use of principal component analysis provided a solution to the challenges of multi-pollutant modelling, it limited the ability to interpret directly the effects of single pollutants. As a result, it remains unclear whether the observed association is driven by one dominant pollutant or by the interaction among multiple components.

5 Conclusions

This study finds that where older adults live in the Netherlands can impact their risk of death from dementia. By linking nine years of region-level mortality data with a rich set of environmental, socio-economic and meteorological indicators, we found three converging lines of evidence:

- **Pollutant mixtures matter more than single pollutants.**

A composite indicator dominated by ozone, cadmium and ammonia (PC4) was a nationwide predictor of mortality after controlling for all the other covariates in the model (2.2% CMF change per standard deviation). In addition, PC1, loaded on heavy metals and combustion-related pollutants, was a predictor of mortality in *Agglomeratie 's-Gravenhage* (13.2% CMF increase per standard deviation). This finding confirms that health-impact assessments must move beyond traditional “one-pollutant-at-a-time” approaches, which still dominate the field, despite growing recognition of the need for multi-pollutant and multi-factorial frameworks (107).

- **Urban form amplifies risk.**

Independent of pollution, every standard deviation (636-person/km²) increase in population density raised mortality by 5.4%, pointing probably to the combined effects of traffic emissions, reduced greenspace and socio-economic stressors that cluster in dense settings.

- **Climate can buffer, or compound, environmental harm.**

Higher sunshine and rainfall were modestly protective, whereas stagnant high-pressure regimes increased risk, underscoring the need to integrate meteorological scenarios into public-health planning.

Taken together, these results call for area-specific interventions rather than one-size-fits-all policies. In highly urbanised regions where industrial and combustion-related emissions are associated with dementia mortality, such as *Agglomeratie 's-Gravenhage*, priority should be given to stricter industrial emissions controls, traffic-related air quality improvements, and the expansion of urban green infrastructure to mitigate exposure and lower the risk of dementia mortality.

Future work should **(i)** link these regional patterns to person-level cohort data, including detailed residential histories, to clarify causal pathways and more accurately estimate the effects of long-term and cumulative environmental exposures, **(ii)** incorporate healthcare system data, social and psychological factors as potential unmeasured confounders, and **(iii)**

assess whether changes in environmental policies, such as reducing emissions, increasing urban greenspace, or implementing low-emission zones, could impact dementia mortality across Dutch regions.

Overall, this study calls for place-specific solutions that integrate environmental and urban interventions into one coherent strategy for reducing dementia deaths.

References

1. American Psychiatric Association, editor. Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders: DSM-IV. 4. ed., 7. print. Washington, DC; 1998. 886 p.
2. 2024 Alzheimer's disease facts and figures. *Alzheimers Dement*. 2024;20(5):3708–821.
3. Mast BT, Yochim BP. Alzheimer's disease and dementia. Göttingen, Germany: Hogrefe; 2018. vii, 76 p. (Alzheimer's disease and dementia).
4. Akhter F, Persaud A, Zaokari Y, Zhao Z, Zhu D. Vascular Dementia and Underlying Sex Differences. *Front Aging Neurosci* [Internet]. 2021 Sep 8 [cited 2025 Jun 1];13. Available from: <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/aging-neuroscience/articles/10.3389/fnagi.2021.720715/full>
5. Li X, Feng X, Sun X, Hou N, Han F, Liu Y. Global, regional, and national burden of Alzheimer's disease and other dementias, 1990–2019. *Front Aging Neurosci* [Internet]. 2022 Oct 10 [cited 2025 May 26];14. Available from: <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/aging-neuroscience/articles/10.3389/fnagi.2022.937486/full>
6. Nichols E, Steinmetz JD, Vollset SE, Fukutaki K, Chalek J, Abd-Allah F, et al. Estimation of the global prevalence of dementia in 2019 and forecasted prevalence in 2050: an analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2019. *Lancet Public Health*. 2022 Feb 1;7(2):e105–25.
7. Lobo A, Launer LJ, Fratiglioni L, Andersen K, Di Carlo A, Breteler MM, et al. Prevalence of dementia and major subtypes in Europe: A collaborative study of population-based cohorts. *Neurologic Diseases in the Elderly Research Group. Neurology*. 2000;54(11 Suppl 5):S4-9.
8. Huque H, Eramudugolla R, Chidiac B, Ee N, Ehrenfeld L, Matthews FE, et al. Could Country-Level Factors Explain Sex Differences in Dementia Incidence and Prevalence? A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *J Alzheimer's Dis*. 2023 Feb 14;91(4):1231–41.
9. Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek. Trends in sterfte en doodsoorzaken, 2014-2024 [Internet]. 2025 [cited 2025 Jun 1]. Available from: <https://www.cbs.nl/nl-nl/longread/statistische-trends/2025/trends-in-sterfte-en-doodsoorzaken-2014-2024>
10. Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek. Oversterfte en doodsoorzaken in 2020 tot en met 2022 [Internet]. 2023 [cited 2025 Jun 4]. Available from: <https://www.cbs.nl/nl-nl/longread/rapportages/2023/oversterfte-en-doodsoorzaken-in-2020-tot-en-met-2022?onepage=true>
11. Mortality DB [Internet]. [cited 2025 Jun 1]. Netherlands. Available from: <https://platform.who.int/mortality/countries/country-details/MDB/netherlands>
12. Livingston G, Huntley J, Sommerlad A, Ames D, Ballard C, Banerjee S, et al. Dementia prevention, intervention, and care: 2020 report of the Lancet Commission. *The Lancet*. 2020 Aug 8;396(10248):413–46.

13. Killin LOJ, Starr JM, Shiue IJ, Russ TC. Environmental risk factors for dementia: a systematic review. *BMC Geriatr*. 2016 Oct 12;16(1):175.
14. Huang X, Steinmetz J, Marsh EK, Aravkin AY, Ashbaugh C, Murray CJL, et al. A systematic review with a Burden of Proof meta-analysis of health effects of long-term ambient fine particulate matter (PM2.5) exposure on dementia. *Nat Aging*. 2025 May;5(5):897–908.
15. Peters S, Bouma F, Hoek G, Janssen N, Vermeulen R. Air pollution exposure and mortality from neurodegenerative diseases in the Netherlands: A population-based cohort study. *Environ Res*. 2024 Oct 15;259:119552.
16. de Crom TOE, Ginos BNR, Oudin A, Ikram MK, Voortman T, Ikram MA. Air Pollution and the Risk of Dementia: The Rotterdam Study. *J Alzheimer's Dis*. 2023 Jan 17;91(2):603–13.
17. van de Vorst IE, Koek HL, Stein CE, Bots ML, Vaartjes I. Socioeconomic Disparities and Mortality After a Diagnosis of Dementia: Results From a Nationwide Registry Linkage Study. *Am J Epidemiol*. 2016 Aug 1;184(3):219–26.
18. Lai KY, Kumari S, Webster C, Gallacher JEJ, Sarkar C. Neighbourhood residential density, urbanicity and incident dementia and Alzheimer's disease: A 12-year prospective cohort study from the UK Biobank. *Environ Res*. 2023 Jun 1;226:115627.
19. World Bank Open Data [Internet]. [cited 2025 Jun 17]. World Bank Open Data. Available from: <https://data.worldbank.org>
20. Elliott P, Wartenberg D. Spatial Epidemiology: Current Approaches and Future Challenges. *Environ Health Perspect*. 2004 Jun;112(9):998–1006.
21. Overview - NUTS - Nomenclature of territorial units for statistics - Eurostat [Internet]. [cited 2025 Jan 28]. Available from: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/nuts>
22. PIANTADOSI S, BYAR DP, GREEN SB. THE ECOLOGICAL FALLACY. *Am J Epidemiol*. 1988 May 1;127(5):893–904.
23. Fortin MJ, Dale MRT, Ver Hoef JM. Spatial Analysis in Ecology. In: *Wiley StatsRef: Statistics Reference Online* [Internet]. John Wiley & Sons, Ltd; 2016 [cited 2025 May 29]. p. 1–13. Available from: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/9781118445112.stat07766.pub2>
24. Tobler WR. A Computer Movie Simulating Urban Growth in the Detroit Region. *Econ Geogr*. 1970;46:234–40.
25. R Core Team. R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing [Internet]. Vienna, Austria: R Foundation for Statistical Computing; 2025. Available from: <https://www.R-project.org/>
26. Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek. Overledenen naar belangrijke doodsoorzaken, leeftijd, geslacht voor Nederland en per landsdeel, provincie, COROP-gebied en grote gemeenten [Internet]. [cited 2025 Mar 15]. Available from: https://opendata.cbs.nl/statline/portal.html?_la=nl&_catalog=CBS&tableId=80202ned&_t_heme=307

27. Jonge E de. cbsodataR: Statistics Netherlands (CBS) Open Data API Client [Internet]. 2024. Available from: <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=cbsodataR>
28. The ICD-10 Classification of Mental and Behavioural Disorders: Clinical descriptions and diagnostic guidelines [Internet]. [cited 2025 Jan 28]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9241544228>
29. European air quality data (interpolated data)- Series [Internet]. [cited 2025 Jan 31]. Available from: <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/datahub/datahubitem-view/82700fbd-2953-467b-be0a-78a520c3a7ef>
30. Application of FAIRMODE Delta tool to evaluate interpolated European air quality maps for 2012 ETC/ACM Technical Paper 2015/2 [Internet]. [cited 2025 May 23]. Available from: https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-atni/products/etc-atni-reports/etcacm_tp_2015_2_delta_evaluation_aqmaps2012
31. Directive - EU - 2024/2881 - EN - EUR-Lex [Internet]. [cited 2025 Jan 31]. Available from: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L_202402881
32. European Environment Agency. Industrial Reporting under the Industrial Emissions Directive 2010/75/EU and European Pollutant Release and Transfer Register Regulation (EC) No 166/2006 Ver 12.0 Mar. 2025 (Spatial data) [Internet]. European Environment Agency; 2025 [cited 2025 May 16]. Available from: <https://sdi.eea.europa.eu/catalogue/srv/api/records/bdae5454-f6a6-484e-9c82-318e101a7547?language=all>
33. Hoisington AJ, Stearns-Yoder KA, Kovacs EJ, Postolache TT, Brenner LA. Airborne Exposure to Pollutants and Mental Health: A Review with Implications for United States Veterans. *Curr Environ Health Rep.* 2024 Jun;11(2):168–83.
34. Lee HJ, Park MK, Seo YR. Pathogenic Mechanisms of Heavy Metal Induced-Alzheimer's Disease. *Toxicol Environ Health Sci.* 2018 Mar 1;10(1):1–10.
35. Human health effects of benzene, arsenic, cadmium, nickel, lead and mercury: report of an expert consultation [Internet]. [cited 2025 Jun 4]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/europe/publications/i/item/WHO-EURO-2023-8983-48755-72523>
36. Humphreys J, Valdés Hernández M del C. Impact of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon exposure on cognitive function and neurodegeneration in humans: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Front Neurol.* 2023 Jan 10;13:1052333.
37. Adlimoghaddam A, Sabbir MG, Albeni BC. Ammonia as a Potential Neurotoxic Factor in Alzheimer's Disease. *Front Mol Neurosci* [Internet]. 2016 Aug 8 [cited 2025 Jun 4];9. Available from: <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/molecular-neuroscience/articles/10.3389/fnmol.2016.00057/full>
38. Ma T, Wang X, He W, Zhang G, Shan T, Song X, et al. Exposure to volatile organic compounds is associated with increased risk of depression: A cross-sectional study. *J Affect Disord.* 2024 Oct 15;363:239–48.
39. Hijmans RJ. terra: Spatial Data Analysis [Internet]. 2025. Available from: <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=terra>

40. Pebesma E. Simple Features for R: Standardized Support for Spatial Vector Data. R J. 2018;10(1):439–46.
41. Pebesma E, Bivand R. Spatial Data Science: With Applications in R. New York: Chapman and Hall/CRC; 2023. 314 p.
42. Climate and energy indicators for Europe from 1979 to present derived from reanalysis [Internet]. [cited 2025 Jan 31]. Available from: <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/datasets/sis-energy-derived-reanalysis?tab=overview>
43. Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek. Huishoudens, Welvaart, Inkomen, Vermogen, Opleidingsniveau, Arbeidsverleden, SES-WOA, Spreiding, 2014-2022 [Internet]. [cited 2025 Mar 15]. Available from: https://opendata.cbs.nl/statline/portal.html?_la=nl&_catalog=CBS&tableId=85900NED&_theme=381
44. Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek. Bevolking op 1 januari en gemiddelde jaarbevolking naar geslacht, leeftijd, burgerlijke staat en regio [Internet]. [cited 2025 Mar 15]. Available from: https://opendata.cbs.nl/portal.html?_la=nl&_catalog=CBS&tableId=03759ned&_theme=278
45. Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek. CBS gebiedsindelingen 2022 [Internet]. [cited 2025 Jun 8]. Available from: <https://www.cbs.nl/nl-nl/dossier/nederland-regionaal/geografische-data/cbs-gebiedsindelingen>
46. Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek. SES-WOA scores per wijk en buurt [Internet]. [cited 2025 Jun 2]. Available from: <https://www.cbs.nl/nl-nl/onze-diensten/methoden/onderzoeksomschrijvingen/korte-onderzoeksomschrijvingen/ses-woa-scores-per-wijk-en-buurt>
47. Database - Income and living conditions - Eurostat [Internet]. [cited 2025 Jan 31]. Available from: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/income-and-living-conditions/database>
48. Julious S, Nicholl J, George S. Why do we continue to use standardized mortality ratios for small area comparisons? J Public Health. 2001 Mar 1;23(1):40–6.
49. Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek. Methods of standardisation [Internet]. [cited 2025 May 25]. Available from: <https://www.cbs.nl/nl-nl/onze-diensten/methoden/statistische-methoden/throughput/throughput/methods-of-standardisation>
50. R Core Team. R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing [Internet]. Vienna, Austria: R Foundation for Statistical Computing; 2025. Available from: <https://www.R-project.org/>
51. Lawson AB. Bayesian Disease Mapping: Hierarchical Modeling in Spatial Epidemiology, Third Edition [Internet]. 3rd ed. New York: Chapman and Hall/CRC; 2018. 486 p. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781351271769>
52. MORAN PAP. NOTES ON CONTINUOUS STOCHASTIC PHENOMENA. Biometrika. 1950 Jun 1;37(1–2):17–23.

53. Bivand RS, Wong DWS. Comparing implementations of global and local indicators of spatial association. *TEST*. 2018 Sep 1;27(3):716–48.
54. Bivand R. R Packages for Analyzing Spatial Data: A Comparative Case Study with Areal Data. *Geogr Anal*. 2022;54(3):488–518.
55. Wickham H. *ggplot2: Elegant Graphics for Data Analysis* [Internet]. Springer-Verlag New York; 2016. Available from: <https://ggplot2.tidyverse.org>
56. Bürkner PC. brms: An R Package for Bayesian Multilevel Models Using Stan. *J Stat Softw*. 2017 Aug 29;80:1–28.
57. Bürkner PC. Advanced Bayesian Multilevel Modeling with the R Package brms. *R J*. 2018;10(1):395–411.
58. Bürkner PC. Bayesian Item Response Modeling in R with brms and Stan. *J Stat Softw*. 2021 Nov 30;100:1–54.
59. Carpenter B, Gelman A, Hoffman MD, Lee D, Goodrich B, Betancourt M, et al. Stan: A Probabilistic Programming Language. *J Stat Softw*. 2017 Jan 11;76:1–32.
60. Sthle L, Wold S. Analysis of variance (ANOVA). *Chemom Intell Lab Syst*. 1989 Nov 1;6(4):259–72.
61. Besag J, York J, Mollié A. Bayesian image restoration, with two applications in spatial statistics. *Ann Inst Stat Math*. 1991 Mar 1;43(1):1–20.
62. Morris M, Wheeler-Martin K, Simpson D, Mooney SJ, Gelman A, DiMaggio C. Bayesian hierarchical spatial models: Implementing the Besag York Mollié model in stan. *Spat Spatio-Temporal Epidemiol*. 2019 Nov;31:100301.
63. Besag J. Spatial Interaction and the Statistical Analysis of Lattice Systems. *J R Stat Soc Ser B Methodol*. 1974;36(2):192–236.
64. Vehtari A, Gelman A, Gabry J. Practical Bayesian model evaluation using leave-one-out cross-validation and WAIC. *Stat Comput*. 2017 Sep;27(5):1413–32.
65. Vehtari A, Gabry J, Magnusson M, Yao Y, Bürkner PC, Paananen T, et al. loo: Efficient Leave-One-Out Cross-Validation and WAIC for Bayesian Models [Internet]. 2024 [cited 2025 Apr 30]. Available from: <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/loo/index.html>
66. Gelman A, Carlin JB, Stern HS, Dunson DB, Vehtari A, Rubin DB. *Bayesian Data Analysis*. 3rd ed. New York: Chapman and Hall/CRC; 2013. 675 p.
67. Gabry J, Simpson D, Vehtari A, Betancourt M, Gelman A. Visualization in Bayesian workflow. *J R Stat Soc Ser A Stat Soc*. 2019 Feb 1;182(2):389–402.
68. Gelman A, Simpson D, Betancourt M. The Prior Can Often Only Be Understood in the Context of the Likelihood. *Entropy*. 2017 Oct 19;19(10):555.
69. GitHub [Internet]. [cited 2025 Apr 3]. Prior Choice Recommendations. Available from: <https://github.com/stan-dev/stan/wiki/Prior-Choice-Recommendations>

70. Kay M. tidybayes: Tidy Data and Geoms for Bayesian Models [Internet]. Zenodo; 2024 [cited 2025 Jun 8]. Available from: <https://zenodo.org/records/13770114>
71. Gelman A, Vehtari A, Simpson D, Margossian CC, Carpenter B, Yao Y, et al. Bayesian Workflow [Internet]. arXiv; 2020 [cited 2025 Mar 21]. Available from: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2011.01808>
72. McElreath R. Statistical Rethinking: A Bayesian Course with Examples in R and STAN. 2nd ed. New York: Chapman and Hall/CRC; 2020. 612 p.
73. Bürkner PC. brms: An R Package for Bayesian Multilevel Models Using Stan. J Stat Softw [Internet]. 2017 [cited 2024 Oct 24];80(1). Available from: <http://www.jstatsoft.org/v80/i01/>
74. Smith TR, Wakefield J, Dobra A. Restricted Covariance Priors with Applications in Spatial Statistics. Bayesian Anal. 2015 Dec;10(4):965–90.
75. van Asten L, Harmsen CN, Stoeldraijer L, Klinkenberg D, Teirlinck AC, de Lange MMA, et al. Excess Deaths during Influenza and Coronavirus Disease and Infection-Fatality Rate for Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2, the Netherlands. Emerg Infect Dis. 2021 Feb;27(2):411–20.
76. Vestergaard LS, Nielsen J, Krause TG, Espenhain L, Tersago K, Bustos Sierra N, et al. Excess all-cause and influenza-attributable mortality in Europe, December 2016 to February 2017. Eurosurveillance. 2017 Apr 6;22(14):30506.
77. International statistical classification of diseases and related health problems. 10th revision, 2010 ed. Geneva: World Health Organization;
78. Medical certification, ICD mortality coding, and reporting mortality associated with COVID-19 [Internet]. [cited 2025 Jun 4]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/WHO-2019-nCoV-mortality-reporting-2020-1>
79. Barría-Sandoval C, Ferreira G, Navarrete JP, Farhang M. The impact of COVID-19 on deaths from dementia and Alzheimer's disease in Chile: an analysis of panel data for 16 regions, 2017–2022. Lancet Reg Health – Am [Internet]. 2024 May 1 [cited 2025 Jun 16];33. Available from: [https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lanam/article/PIIS2667-193X\(24\)00053-X/fulltext](https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lanam/article/PIIS2667-193X(24)00053-X/fulltext)
80. Seshadri S, Wolf PA, Beiser A, Au R, McNulty K, White R, et al. Lifetime risk of dementia and Alzheimer's disease. Neurology. 1997 Dec;49(6):1498–504.
81. Gong J, Harris K, Lipnicki DM, Castro-Costa E, Lima-Costa MF, Diniz BS, et al. Sex differences in dementia risk and risk factors: Individual-participant data analysis using 21 cohorts across six continents from the COSMIC consortium. Alzheimers Dement. 2023;19(8):3365–78.
82. Peckham H, de Gruijter NM, Raine C, Radziszewska A, Ciurtin C, Wedderburn LR, et al. Male sex identified by global COVID-19 meta-analysis as a risk factor for death and ICU admission. Nat Commun. 2020 Dec 9;11(1):6317.
83. Caram-Deelder C, Vlieg A van H, Groenwold RHH, Chen Q, Mook-Kanamori DO, Dekkers OM, et al. Excess mortality during the first 2 years of the COVID-19 pandemic (2020-2021)

- in the Netherlands: Overall and across demographic subgroups. *IJID Reg.* 2025 Mar 1;14:100500.
84. Niessen A, Teirlinck AC, McDonald SA, van der Hoek W, van Gageldonk-Lafeber R, Knol MJ, et al. Sex differences in COVID-19 mortality in the Netherlands. *Infection.* 2022 Jun 1;50(3):709–17.
 85. Yoshida Y, Wang J, Zu Y. Sex differences in comorbidities and COVID-19 mortality—Report from the real-world data. *Front Public Health* [Internet]. 2022 Aug 12 [cited 2025 Jun 16];10. Available from: <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/public-health/articles/10.3389/fpubh.2022.881660/full>
 86. Cerza F, Renzi M, Gariazzo C, Davoli M, Michelozzi P, Forastiere F, et al. Long-term exposure to air pollution and hospitalization for dementia in the Rome longitudinal study. *Environ Health.* 2019 Aug 9;18(1):72.
 87. Chau-Ren Jung, Yu-Ting Lin, and Bing-Fang Hwang. Ozone, Particulate Matter, and Newly Diagnosed Alzheimer's Disease: A Population-Based Cohort Study in Taiwan. [cited 2025 May 12]; Available from: <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/epdf/10.3233/JAD-140855>
 88. Wu YC, Lin YC, Yu HL, Chen JH, Chen TF, Sun Y, et al. Association between air pollutants and dementia risk in the elderly. *Alzheimers Dement Diagn Assess Dis Monit.* 2015 Jun 1;1(2):220–8.
 89. Carey IM, Anderson HR, Atkinson RW, Beevers SD, Cook DG, Strachan DP, et al. Are noise and air pollution related to the incidence of dementia? A cohort study in London, England. *BMJ Open.* 2018 Sep 1;8(9):e022404.
 90. Shi L, Steenland K, Li H, Liu P, Zhang Y, Lyles RH, et al. A national cohort study (2000–2018) of long-term air pollution exposure and incident dementia in older adults in the United States. *Nat Commun.* 2021 Nov 19;12(1):6754.
 91. Chen H, Kwong JC, Copes R, Hystad P, van Donkelaar A, Tu K, et al. Exposure to ambient air pollution and the incidence of dementia: A population-based cohort study. *Environ Int.* 2017 Nov 1;108:271–7.
 92. Min JY, Min KB. Blood cadmium levels and Alzheimer's disease mortality risk in older US adults. *Environ Health Glob Access Sci Source.* 2016 Jun 14;15(1):69.
 93. Peng Q, Bakulski KM, Nan B, Park SK. Cadmium and Alzheimer's Disease Mortality in U.S. Adults: Updated Evidence with a Urinary Biomarker and Extended Follow-up Time. *Environ Res.* 2017 Aug;157:44–51.
 94. Shi L, Zhu Q, Wang Y, Hao H, Zhang H, Schwartz J, et al. Incident dementia and long-term exposure to constituents of fine particle air pollution: A national cohort study in the United States. *Proc Natl Acad Sci.* 2023 Jan 3;120(1):e2211282119.
 95. Marin-Castañeda L, Gonzalez-Garibay G, Garcia-Quintana I, Pacheco Aispuro G, Rubio C. Mechanisms of ozone-induced neurotoxicity in the development and progression of dementia: a brief review. *Front Aging Neurosci.* 2024 Oct 28;

96. Forcella M, Lau P, Oldani M, Melchiorretto P, Bogni A, Gribaldo L, et al. Neuronal specific and non-specific responses to cadmium possibly involved in neurodegeneration: A toxicogenomics study in a human neuronal cell model. *NeuroToxicology*. 2020 Jan 1;76:162–73.
97. Sanders AP, Claus Henn B, Wright RO. Perinatal and Childhood Exposure to Cadmium, Manganese, and Metal Mixtures and Effects on Cognition and Behavior: A Review of Recent Literature. *Curr Environ Health Rep*. 2015 Sep 1;2(3):284–94.
98. EEA. Air pollution in Europe: 2024 reporting status under the National Emission reduction Commitments Directive [Internet]. [cited 2025 May 16]. Available from: <https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/national-emission-reduction-commitments-directive-2024/air-pollution-in-europe-2024>
99. Seiler N. Is ammonia a pathogenetic factor in Alzheimer's disease? *Neurochem Res*. 1993 Mar 1;18(3):235–45.
100. Adlimoghaddam A, Sabbir MG, Albensi BC. Ammonia as a Potential Neurotoxic Factor in Alzheimer's Disease. *Front Mol Neurosci* [Internet]. 2016 Aug 8 [cited 2025 May 13];9. Available from: <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/molecular-neuroscience/articles/10.3389/fnmol.2016.00057/full>
101. Cabral Pinto MMS, Marinho-Reis P, Almeida A, Pinto E, Neves O, Inácio M, et al. Links between Cognitive Status and Trace Element Levels in Hair for an Environmentally Exposed Population: A Case Study in the Surroundings of the Estarreja Industrial Area. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2019 Jan;16(22):4560.
102. Weuve J, D'Souza J, Beck T, Evans DA, Kaufman JD, Rajan Kumar B, et al. Long-term community noise exposure in relation to dementia, cognition, and cognitive decline in older adults. *Alzheimers Dement*. 2021;17(3):525–33.
103. Gascon M, Triguero-Mas M, Martínez D, Dadvand P, Fornes J, Plasència A, et al. Mental Health Benefits of Long-Term Exposure to Residential Green and Blue Spaces: A Systematic Review. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2015 Apr;12(4):4354–79.
104. Modai-Snir T, and van Ham M. Reordering, inequality and divergent growth: processes of neighbourhood change in Dutch cities. *Reg Stud*. 2020 Dec 1;54(12):1668–79.
105. Vautard R, Beekmann M, Desplat J, Hodzic A, Morel S. Air quality in Europe during the summer of 2003 as a prototype of air quality in a warmer climate. *Comptes Rendus Géoscience*. 2007;339(11–12):747–63.
106. Kontis V, Bennett JE, Rashid T, Parks RM, Pearson-Stuttard J, Guillot M, et al. Magnitude, demographics and dynamics of the effect of the first wave of the COVID-19 pandemic on all-cause mortality in 21 industrialized countries. *Nat Med*. 2020 Dec;26(12):1919–28.
107. Traini E, Huss A, Portengen L, Rookus M, Verschuren WMM, Vermeulen RCH, et al. A Multipollutant Approach to Estimating Causal Effects of Air Pollution Mixtures on Overall Mortality in a Large, Prospective Cohort. *Epidemiology*. 2022 Jul;33(4):514.

Appendix A

Supplementary Table 1. Region names and codes

Dutch Regions: Codes and Names	
Region Code	Region Name
CR01	Oost-Groningen
CR02	Delfzijl en omgeving
CR03	Overig Groningen
CR04	Noord-Friesland
CR05	Zuidwest-Friesland
CR06	Zuidoost-Friesland
CR07	Noord-Drenthe
CR08	Zuidoost-Drenthe
CR09	Zuidwest-Drenthe
CR10	Noord-Overijssel
CR11	Zuidwest-Overijssel
CR12	Twente
CR13	Veluwe
CR14	Achterhoek
CR15	Arnhem/Nijmegen
CR16	Zuidwest-Gelderland
CR17	Utrecht
CR18	Kop van Noord-Holland
CR19	Alkmaar en omgeving
CR20	IJmond
CR21	Agglomeratie Haarlem
CR22	Zaanstreek
CR23	Groot-Amsterdam
CR24	Het Gooi en Vechtstreek
CR25	Agglomeratie Leiden en Bollenstreek
CR26	Agglomeratie 's-Gravenhage
CR27	Delft en Westland
CR28	Oost-Zuid-Holland
CR29	Groot-Rijnmond
CR30	Zuidoost-Zuid-Holland
CR31	Zeeuwsch-Vlaanderen
CR32	Overig Zeeland
CR33	West-Noord-Brabant
CR34	Midden-Noord-Brabant
CR35	Noordoost-Noord-Brabant
CR36	Zuidoost-Noord-Brabant
CR37	Noord-Limburg
CR38	Midden-Limburg
CR39	Zuid-Limburg
CR40	Flevoland

Supplementary Table 2. Summary of priors used in the models

(a)

Summary of Priors Used in Model 1		
Parameter	class	Prior Distribution
Air Temperature	b	normal(0, 0.05)
Global Horizontal Irradiance	b	normal(0, 0.05)
Mean Sea Level Pressure	b	normal(0, 0.05)
Mean SES	b	normal(0, 0.05)
PC2	b	normal(0, 0.05)
PC3	b	normal(0, 0.05)
PC4	b	normal(0, 0.05)
Population Density	b	normal(0, 0.05)
Sex: Male	b	normal(0, 0.05)
Total Precipitation	b	normal(0, 0.05)
Wind Speed	b	normal(0, 0.05)
	Intercept	normal(0, 0.05)
Intercept	sd	student_t(3, 0, 0.02)
PC1	sd	student_t(3, 0, 0.05)
	sigma	student_t(3, 0, 0.005)

(b)

Summary of Priors Used in Model 2		
Parameter	class	Prior Distribution
Air Temperature	b	normal(0, 0.05)
Global Horizontal Irradiance	b	normal(0, 0.05)
Mean Sea Level Pressure	b	normal(0, 0.05)
Mean SES	b	normal(0, 0.05)
PC1	b	normal(0, 0.05)
PC2	b	normal(0, 0.05)
PC3	b	normal(0, 0.05)
PC4	b	normal(0, 0.05)
Population Density	b	normal(0, 0.05)
Sex: Male	b	normal(0, 0.05)
Total Precipitation	b	normal(0, 0.05)
Wind Speed	b	normal(0, 0.05)
	rhocar	beta(0.5, 0.5)
	sdcar	student_t(3, 0, 1)
	sigma	student_t(3, 0, 0.005)

Supplementary Table 3. Share of categories F01-F03

Year	Dementia Mortality as a Share of All Mental Disorders		
	Dementia (F01-F03)	All Mental & Behavioural Disorders (F01-F99)	Share of Dementia (%)
2014	9,278	9,764	95.02
2015	10,300	10,875	94.71
2016	10,815	11,420	94.70
2017	11,407	12,033	94.80
2018	11,866	12,432	95.45
2019	11,586	12,200	94.97
2020	10,396	11,055	94.04
2021	10,435	11,125	93.80
2022	11,587	12,343	93.88
Average (2014–2022)	10,852	11,472	94.60

Supplementary Table 4. Top three and bottom three CMF values for females by COROP region.
 The table shows the three COROP regions with the highest and lowest Comparative Mortality Figures for dementia among (a) females and (b) males. Regions are identified by their COROP code and name.

(a)

Region Code	Region Name	Sex	CMF
Female - Top 3			
CR21	Agglomeratie Haarlem	female	1.34
CR31	Zeeuwsch-Vlaanderen	female	1.25
CR24	Het Gooi en Vechtstreek	female	1.21
Female - Bottom 3			
CR19	Alkmaar en omgeving	female	0.66
CR40	Flevoland	female	0.60
CR18	Kop van Noord-Holland	female	0.58

(b)

Region Code	Region Name	Sex	CMF
Male - Top 3			
CR31	Zeeuwsch-Vlaanderen	male	1.30
CR21	Agglomeratie Haarlem	male	1.24
CR24	Het Gooi en Vechtstreek	male	1.22
Male - Bottom 3			
CR18	Kop van Noord-Holland	male	0.72
CR19	Alkmaar en omgeving	male	0.70
CR40	Flevoland	male	0.59

Supplementary Table 5. Correlation matrix of all key study variables, including emissions, air pollutants, meteorological factors, and socio-economic indicators.

		Correlation Matrix																						
Variable	Mean SES	Population Density	PM10	PM2.5	NO2	NOx	O3	Air Temperature	Global Horizontal Irradiance	Mean Sea Level Pressure	Total Precipitation	Wind Speed	Ammonia (NH3)	SOx	Cadmium (Cd)	Methane (CH4)	CO	Mercury (Hg)	NMVOCS	Benzene	Arsenic (As)	PAHs	Lead (Pb)	
Mean SES	1.00	0.35	0.13	0.07	0.30	0.29	-0.03	0.31	0.14	0.10	0.09	0.04	-0.11	-0.05	0.12	0.02	0.06	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.01	0.12
Population Density	0.35	1.00	0.20	-0.02	0.57	0.51	-0.24	0.20	0.27	0.01	0.04	0.28	-0.16	-0.24	-0.15	-0.16	-0.13	-0.05	0.30	0.12	0.05	0.23	0.20	-0.15
PM10	0.13	0.20	1.00	0.91	0.74	0.69	-0.19	0.43	0.27	0.01	-0.21	-0.31	-0.16	-0.21	-0.15	-0.20	-0.02	-0.03	0.30	0.12	0.05	0.23	0.20	-0.15
PM2.5	0.07	-0.02	0.91	1.00	0.60	0.55	-0.30	0.17	0.27	0.01	-0.21	-0.31	-0.16	-0.21	-0.15	-0.20	-0.02	-0.03	0.30	0.12	0.05	0.23	0.20	-0.15
NO2	0.30	0.57	0.74	0.60	1.00	0.96	-0.35	0.34	0.27	0.01	-0.21	-0.31	-0.16	-0.21	-0.15	-0.20	-0.02	-0.03	0.30	0.12	0.05	0.23	0.20	-0.15
NOx	0.29	0.51	0.69	0.55	0.96	1.00	-0.34	0.32	0.29	0.01	-0.21	-0.31	-0.16	-0.21	-0.15	-0.20	-0.02	-0.03	0.30	0.12	0.05	0.23	0.20	-0.15
O3	-0.03	-0.24	-0.19	-0.30	-0.35	-0.34	1.00	0.44	0.27	0.01	-0.21	-0.31	-0.16	-0.21	-0.15	-0.20	-0.02	-0.03	0.30	0.12	0.05	0.23	0.20	-0.15
Air Temperature	0.31	0.20	0.43	0.17	0.34	0.32	0.44	1.00	0.14	0.01	-0.08	-0.06	-0.05	0.07	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06
Global Horizontal Irradiance	0.14	0.27	0.20	-0.49	-0.09	-0.06	0.50	0.43	1.00	0.19	-0.08	-0.06	-0.05	0.07	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06
Mean Sea Level Pressure	0.10	0.01	-0.21	-0.24	-0.01	0.06	0.02	-0.25	0.19	1.00	-0.08	-0.06	-0.05	0.07	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06
Total Precipitation	0.09	0.04	-0.31	-0.20	-0.14	-0.14	-0.52	-0.35	-0.46	-0.08	1.00	0.13	-0.07	-0.02	-0.06	-0.07	-0.02	-0.03	0.30	0.12	0.05	0.23	0.20	-0.15
Wind Speed	0.04	0.28	-0.16	-0.24	-0.15	-0.16	-0.13	-0.05	0.30	-0.21	0.13	1.00	-0.34	0.06	-0.07	-0.02	0.00	-0.03	0.30	0.12	0.05	0.23	0.20	-0.15
Ammonia (NH3)	-0.11	-0.25	0.22	0.20	0.08	0.10	0.09	0.22	0.12	0.12	-0.07	-0.34	1.00	-0.04	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06
SOx	-0.05	0.12	0.15	0.07	0.25	0.26	-0.13	0.07	0.06	0.01	-0.02	0.06	-0.04	1.00	-0.01	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06
Cadmium (Cd)	0.12	-0.02	0.06	0.03	0.02	0.04	0.17	0.10	0.04	-0.01	-0.06	-0.07	0.06	-0.01	1.00	-0.06	0.07	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03
Methane (CH4)	0.02	-0.14	0.09	0.11	0.10	0.11	0.02	0.13	-0.10	0.05	0.00	-0.20	0.06	0.24	-0.06	1.00	-0.04	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
CO	0.06	0.11	0.02	-0.05	0.04	0.02	-0.05	0.03	0.10	-0.03	0.02	0.23	-0.02	0.34	0.07	-0.04	1.00	0.07	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03
Mercury (Hg)	-0.03	0.30	0.12	0.05	0.23	0.20	-0.15	0.00	0.04	-0.03	-0.03	0.15	-0.08	0.33	0.03	0.00	0.71	1.00	0.35	0.34	0.34	0.34	0.34	0.34
NMVOCS	-0.05	0.14	0.18	0.12	0.31	0.32	-0.12	0.13	0.03	0.00	-0.02	-0.04	0.07	0.89	-0.01	0.26	0.12	0.35	1.00	0.93	0.93	0.93	0.93	0.93
Benzene	-0.10	0.11	0.17	0.11	0.27	0.27	-0.11	0.13	0.03	-0.01	-0.01	-0.03	0.13	0.84	-0.02	0.27	0.13	0.34	0.93	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Arsenic (As)	0.09	0.08	0.07	0.03	0.09	0.06	-0.06	0.02	0.02	-0.01	0.02	0.16	-0.04	0.21	0.09	-0.02	0.82	0.58	0.92	0.92	0.92	0.92	0.92	0.92
PAHs	0.11	0.11	-0.08	-0.09	0.00	-0.02	-0.06	0.01	0.11	-0.01	0.04	0.22	-0.07	0.25	0.06	-0.06	0.93	0.63	0.93	0.93	0.93	0.93	0.93	0.93
Lead (Pb)	0.12	0.08	0.08	0.03	0.10	0.08	-0.05	0.04	0.01	-0.02	0.02	0.13	0.02	0.25	0.21	-0.04	0.83	0.62	0.93	0.93	0.93	0.93	0.93	0.93

Supplementary Table 6. PCA loadings

Principal Component Loadings (coloured by sign)

	PC1	PC2	PC3	PC4
mean_PM10	-0.215	-0.343	0.307	-0.137
mean_PM25	-0.169	-0.334	0.312	-0.083
mean_NO2	-0.259	-0.343	0.22	0.09
mean_NOx	-0.249	-0.343	0.194	0.073
mean_O3	0.132	0.141	-0.108	-0.555
HGANDCOMPOUNDS	-0.359	0.169	-0.037	0.105
PBANDCOMPOUNDS	-0.322	0.29	0.159	-0.118
CDANDCOMPOUNDS	-0.039	0.046	0.09	-0.532
ASANDCOMPOUNDS	-0.303	0.295	0.18	-0.03
PAHS	-0.286	0.333	0.1	0.044
BENZENE	-0.265	-0.17	-0.455	-0.079
CO	-0.337	0.331	0.088	-0.008
NMVOC	-0.274	-0.18	-0.452	-0.046
SOX	-0.326	-0.071	-0.415	0.021
CH4	-0.072	-0.122	-0.199	-0.135
NH3	-0.028	-0.109	0.05	-0.561

Supplementary Table 7. P-value for interaction of each covariate with region

P-values for interaction of each covariate with region		
Covariate	F value (interaction)	p-value (interaction)
PC 1	2.00	0.000
PC 3	1.88	0.001
PC 2	1.83	0.002
Population Density	1.56	0.018
Mean SES	1.46	0.036
Mean Sea Level Pressure	1.34	0.086
Sex	1.12	0.281
Global Horizontal Irradiance	0.99	0.494
Total Precipitation	0.91	0.627
Air Temperature	0.85	0.724
Wind Speed	0.83	0.754
PC 4	0.68	0.928

Supplementary Table 8. Posterior predictive checks by region

Posterior predictive check by region		
Observed CMF compared to 95% posterior predictive interval		
Region	95% posterior predictive interval	Observed CMF
CR01	1.83 – 3.27	0.88
CR02	2.06 – 3.67	1.00
CR03	2.38 – 4.30	1.17
CR04	1.82 – 3.24	0.88
CR05	1.77 – 3.16	0.86
CR06	2.01 – 3.57	0.98
CR07	2.08 – 3.69	1.01
CR08	2.03 – 3.60	0.99
CR09	2.04 – 3.64	1.00
CR10	2.07 – 3.63	1.01
CR11	2.32 – 4.08	1.13
CR12	2.47 – 4.38	1.20
CR13	2.01 – 3.51	0.98
CR14	2.11 – 3.72	1.03
CR15	2.22 – 3.94	1.09
CR16	1.87 – 3.27	0.90
CR17	2.06 – 3.61	1.00
CR18	1.49 – 2.56	0.65
CR19	1.53 – 2.65	0.68
CR20	1.85 – 3.25	0.90
CR21	2.66 – 4.79	1.29
CR22	1.93 – 3.42	0.94
CR23	1.70 – 2.95	0.80
CR24	2.48 – 4.44	1.21
CR25	2.17 – 3.85	1.07
CR26	2.26 – 4.37	1.14
CR27	1.67 – 2.90	0.77
CR28	1.72 – 3.02	0.82
CR29	2.14 – 3.77	1.05
CR30	2.27 – 4.14	1.13
CR31	2.62 – 4.80	1.28
CR32	1.99 – 3.52	0.98
CR33	2.16 – 3.82	1.07
CR34	1.99 – 3.56	0.98
CR35	2.04 – 3.57	0.99
CR36	2.04 – 3.74	1.01
CR37	1.89 – 3.31	0.91
CR38	2.18 – 3.92	1.08
CR39	2.28 – 4.08	1.12
CR40	1.42 – 2.47	0.60

Supplementary Table 9. Posterior predictive checks by region. Model with wider priors

Posterior predictive check by region Model with wider priors		
Observed CMF compared to 95% posterior predictive interval		
Region	95% posterior predictive interval	Observed CMF
CR01	1.90 – 3.30	0.92
CR02	1.92 – 3.31	0.92
CR03	2.34 – 4.15	1.15
CR04	1.81 – 3.16	0.88
CR05	1.82 – 3.19	0.88
CR06	1.96 – 3.43	0.96
CR07	2.05 – 3.62	1.00
CR08	1.96 – 3.47	0.97
CR09	2.02 – 3.54	0.99
CR10	2.08 – 3.59	1.01
CR11	2.28 – 4.01	1.12
CR12	2.40 – 4.19	1.16
CR13	2.01 – 3.46	0.97
CR14	2.03 – 3.47	0.97
CR15	2.16 – 3.74	1.05
CR16	1.91 – 3.29	0.92
CR17	2.04 – 3.54	1.00
CR18	1.44 – 2.44	0.60
CR19	1.47 – 2.49	0.62
CR20	1.81 – 3.14	0.86
CR21	2.62 – 4.72	1.28
CR22	1.97 – 3.43	0.96
CR23	1.73 – 2.97	0.81
CR24	2.39 – 4.32	1.19
CR25	2.24 – 3.97	1.10
CR26	2.46 – 4.45	1.21
CR27	1.73 – 2.95	0.80
CR28	1.77 – 3.12	0.86
CR29	2.17 – 3.77	1.06
CR30	2.32 – 4.15	1.16
CR31	2.59 – 4.66	1.27
CR32	1.91 – 3.33	0.93
CR33	2.15 – 3.74	1.05
CR34	2.06 – 3.59	1.01
CR35	2.02 – 3.49	0.98
CR36	2.10 – 3.71	1.03
CR37	1.90 – 3.30	0.91
CR38	2.15 – 3.73	1.04
CR39	2.30 – 4.02	1.12
CR40	1.46 – 2.47	0.61

Supplementary Table 10. Summary of the prior predictive distribution. Shown are the 1st quartile, median, 3rd quartile, the number of draws below zero and above five, and the total percentage of implausible values

Prior Predictive Distribution Summary	
Key Quantiles and Implausible Draws	
Statistic	Value
1st Quartile	0.90
Median	1.00
3rd Quartile	1.11
Draws < 0	33.00
Draws > 5	3207.00
Total Implausible (%)	0.02

Supplementary Table 11. Comparison of prior and posterior standard deviations for fixed and group-level parameters. The table presents the standard deviations (SD) of the prior and posterior distributions for each model parameter, along with an indication of whether the prior was informative.

Comparison of Prior and Posterior Standard Deviations			
Fixed and Group-level Parameters			
Parameter	Prior SD	Posterior SD	Informative Prior
Intercept	0.050	0.010	Yes
Mean SES	0.050	0.008	Yes
Population Density	0.050	0.009	Yes
Global Horizontal Irradiance	0.050	0.013	Yes
Air Temperature	0.050	0.011	Yes
Mean Sea Level Pressure	0.050	0.009	Yes
Total Precipitation	0.050	0.009	Yes
Wind Speed	0.050	0.009	Yes
Sex: Male	0.050	0.014	Yes
PC1	0.050	0.008	Yes
PC2	0.050	0.009	Yes
PC3	0.050	0.008	Yes
PC4	0.050	0.008	Yes
Residual SD	0.005	0.005	Yes